

>> Jimmy Corsetti's Theory on the Lost City of Atlantis (https://youtu.be/o_R1zoY9kWs)

Ashes of Atlantis - Journal Series #1:

An EPEMC response¹ to Jimmy Corsetti's Richat hypothesis on the Joe Rogan Podcast

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
Lexington, KY

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Re: The Eye of the Sahara as Atlantis

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC^{2 3}, <http://www.epemcgateway.com>

Dear Readers,

I have been meaning to write a follow-up paper to "Unboxing Atlantis" for some time. I wrote the paper *before* Jimmy released his hypothesis. I presented the link to him *as he was presenting his ideas* in 2019, and to Matt of "Ancient Architects." However, the evidence was ignored, which is fine. I am a "fan" (both a sub and an advocate) of both of them, and I particularly like Jimmy. However, Mr. Corsetti's hypothesis is clearly and definitively incorrect for all of the following reasons:

1. That region of Africa has not been submerged in over 99 million years⁴, and its uplift and downthrust values are stable
2. At the time of the Younger Dryas, the sea level was **lower** and could not have made the richat area an island.
3. The richat formation is not concentrically circular.
4. It could never act as canals or hold water.
5. It is itself on a tilt (and we will look at the topographics and satellite data on this)
6. There are no mountains immediately to the north.
7. The Atlas Mountains are named for King Atlas, who was named for Atlantis (perhaps), not vice versa.
8. The regions is not 1000 miles past the Pillars of Heracles (straits of Gibraltar)
9. The whale carcasses found are from clear fluvial megatsunami inundation, as Jimmy himself points out.

¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>

²

https://www.academia.edu/37569958/EPEMC_tm_Benefits_Ten_Reasons_to_Consider_Switching_to_Extended_Plasma_electromagnetic_Cosmology

³ https://www.academia.edu/50912946/FAQ_EPEMC_MIMS

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Richat_Structure

I actually like Jimmy quite a lot⁵. Therefore I am reluctant on this, but as the JRE podcast reaches millions of altstreamers, I must provide a scientific response fact by fact to the podcast. I don't mind that people have pet theories, almost all do. However, Jimmy had the chance to review the data I and others provided⁶, and science is not about making friends but about eliminating poor hypotheses.

The Richat is almost certainly an electrical scar⁷ from arc connection, likely with the moon or Kingu (now destroyed) or Tiamat (now the Trojan asteroid belt)⁸. In electrogeology⁹ we would expect massive climate changes, and in the Sahara we see this at the 5-7kya boundary¹⁰. It is expected for the whale remains to be less than that in [unreliable] carbon dating. I say unreliable because of the electrical environment. Close study has shown that objects, particularly OOPArts¹¹ that have errant carbon dating usually are proximal to electrical systems¹², if they are not simply diffusionist issues. Mining hammers, spark plugs, metal objects, most of which are found in coal or mineral deposits, all of which can be created in rapid electrical scenarios whose exact properties are not yet disclosed. We are in the early stages of finding stone in situ¹³, looking at macroscopic evidence^{14 15}, and doing rough lab work¹⁶ to show formation processes¹⁷. As for how the nuclear transmutation¹⁸ is occurring, it is still - at present - a mystery¹⁹. We only know that it *is* happening and *probably* is related to a structured atomic model²⁰ enhancement of the standard model of the quantum nuclear model of the atom.²¹

Reluctantly, therefore, I will go through and respond to this video, both Joe and Jimmy, with particular timestamps. This is important for the altstream to do and become better at peer review. We never want to get to the nepotism and cliquishness of the mainstream, and the hypocrisy of the "cults of personality." I see that happening easily with Youtube and social media. I am not saying that's happening here, but let's ensure that it doesn't.

⁵ Under better circumstances I think we could share a beer (I'd buy for a veteran!) and I'd blow his mind with the real history of humanity.

⁶

https://www.academia.edu/36753644/Unboxing_Atlantis_A_top_down_review_of_what_we_know_and_dont_know_about_the_Atlantean_through_Megalithic_Period_continents_and_cities_36_000_2_000_YBP

⁷ Specifically a large form of Kimberly Pipe known as a "salt dome" in the same vein as Upheaval Dome and potentially Hicks Dome. It is almost certainly the result of an electrical cryptoexplosive process and there will be probable magnetic **but not gravitic** anomalies on the site, as with Hicks Dome. See footnote 13.

⁸ See The Enuma Elish, tablets 4 and 5.

⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology>

¹⁰ The Jovian era, overlap with late Archaic to early Megalithic Periods; see Appendix A, Figure 23

¹¹ "MIMS 2.0.1.1-3 : The Threefold Science," part 1, <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

¹² <https://bit.ly/3d2L28f>

¹³ https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge

¹⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/m-steinbacher>

¹⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fDIRMB3hVQM>

¹⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/gable>

¹⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/yelverton>

¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5Y4K7YjRnB4>

¹⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yXjL8-ViwEo&list=PLeeyNowkGd8MFPZHfYVYaVgoZFMhg_F49

²⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L2peoqu7ho>

²¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/atomic-models>

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Timestamped Record of Claims

1. 0:18 Joe, "The Younger Dryas Impact Theory²² (YDIT) the concept that somewhere in the roughly around 11k 12k years ago that we were hit by a series of comets. And it's pretty evident *that that's a fact if you do the core samples of the Earth, they find this nuclear glass all over the Earth that exists in that time period.*"
2. 0:38 Joe, "And it seems like something happened that reset civilization."
3. 0:43 Joe, "There is very little evidence of advanced civilization before that up until recently... the last couple of decades. They discovered Gobekli Tepe and all these other structures that are clearly from more than 12k years ago. And they're really complex with enormous stones."
4. 1:03 Joe "It's sort of caused people to rethink the history of the Earth... of human civilizations. And Atlantis has always been the big one... no one can figure out where it is, or if it's real."
5. 1:35 Jimmy, "I think [Atlantis] represented a civilization that was doing great things. They were more global than what people think would be possible."
6. 1:48 Jimmy, "Atlantis was said to be a kingdom... an empire made up of 10 kingdoms. And then there was the lost city of Atlantis which was the capital, which was said to be made up of concentric circles. Two of water, three of land."
7. 2:02 Jimmy, "Essentially they were obliterated by a cataclysm, passed down by Plato... who got the story from Solon who was his uncle separated by 5 generations.... It's the ancient Egyptians where that tale comes from."
8. 3:10 Jimmy, "By the way, you see that? That white... those blemishes... that's salt. This was under the ocean."
9. 3:25 Jimmy, "So let me say there's absolute doubt. Even I am not 100% certain. I'm not even 100% certain Atlantis existed. What I am sure of is that Atlanteans were doing spectacular things and ... a cataclysmic event happened called the Younger Dryas."
10. 3:50 Jimmy, "The consensus is it's a volcanic dome that had risen and collapsed multiple times, like a hundred million years ago... I would like to know where they get these figures from..."
11. 4:10 Jimmy, "Here we are talking about how crazy things changed in just the last 12, 13k years. So when they throw around these numbers... 1 million years is an incredibly long time."
12. 4:30 Joe, "Well the problem is there's these concentric circles... I've never seen anything... I'm not an archaeologist... but I've never seen anything like this... I mean if you study structures that are man made structures, I've never seen anything like this that humans have made."
13. 5:00 Jimmy, "So what you're looking at is approximately 250 miles inland, a total barren desert of Mauritania, Africa."
14. 5:25 Jimmy, "It's essentially a satellite imagery that they enhanced in order for you to see the difference in elevation and actual structure itself."
15. 5:32 Joe, "It would be these concentric circles that are raised above the water, and then the water would be inside of it like that."
16. 5:42 Jimmy, "... this particular image: no this is not trying to represent water. That blue is actually picking up on salt."
17. 5:50 Joe, "That's salt because it used to be under water?"
18. 5:52 Jimmy, "That's what I believe, and that's what makes the most sense to me. Others will disagree, and let me tell you why."
19. 5:57 Jimmy, "It is currently 12, 1300 feet above sea level, and 250 miles inland."
20. 6:05 Jimmy, "It was not under the ocean for at least... 10s of millions of years is what scientists claim. I argue that since the salt is still there..."

²² Zamora, Carlson, Hancock et al.

21. 6:23 Jimmy, "Those areas with the most white blemishes happen to be the areas with the lowest in elevation, which tells me that saltwater had settled there."
22. 6:33 Jimmy, "Atlantis was said to ... be open to the sea to the south."
23. 6:50 Joe, "It's a very flat area that looks like it's the lowest elevation, around it looks like it's higher."
[orthogonal vector]
24. 7:24 Jimmy, "All that white is salt. In fact I have a friend, Joss [inaudible] that went out there and tasted that shit off the fucking ground and that's salt. (sic) Because a lot of people say 'This was never under the ocean.'"
25. 7:35 Jimmy, "Even Randall Carlson himself, which let me just say he - for a few reasons - he... favors the Azores... he doesn't think this would likely be the locations... the island chain which would be ... to him he's partial towards that."
26. 7:57 Jimmy, "He analyzed this site, you see all the striations? It looks like the ocean... or... that's all water erosion Joe. So remember when Randall was on your show, and he showed you the Missoula Flood Plains, and all those giant ripples from the giant current that went through?"
27. 8:19 Jimmy, "You're going to see those same water ripples... 'cause ... this structure is many miles... 30 miles across."
28. 8:27 Joe, "That's crazy, what looks like the bottom of the ocean, like if you see where the water breaks on the bottom of the sand."
29. 8:37 Jimmy, "that white is salt, and... cause a lot of people don't know the Sahara desert wasn't a thing until approximately 5k years ago. It's only in the last several years... and by the way I'm quoting MIT research here... that the Sahara goes back and forth from green to desert approximately every 20k years. They believe it has something to do with the Earth's tilt. And that's with discussing.²³"
30. 9:03 Jimmy, "Because people are like 'well that's not Atlantis.'²⁴ ... First of all, if this whole... this west... the Sahara desert was a lush green tropical paradise, which had the largest known freshwater lakes ever known to have existed. For example megalake Chad, which is like 3 times the water surface than all the Great Lakes combined. It's a big sucker."
31. 9:27 Joe, "holy shit... how is that not an ocean? Was that fresh water?"
32. 9:31 Jimmy²⁵, "It was, when it existed, and that was at the time when the Sahara was green. And it also had some of the largest rivers known to have existed..."
33. 9:51 Jimmy, "Cause one of the arguments I make is that the fact that that salt is on top of the dirt, is indicative that the ocean flowed over here far more recently than what people think."
34. 10:08 Jimmy, "The circles themselves are about fourteen and a half miles across, however if you go the complete shebang, the whole circle itself is just shy of 30 miles."
35. 10:19 Joe, "So the whole thing is 30 miles, which would be like the size of a city."

²³ Indeed, Ben Davidson from the Suspicious Observers and Dr. Vogt would agree. The Earth did absolutely turn over, but there isn't super strong knowledge about the tilt vectors, as of yet. Regardless, it would be difficult to pin down with our current knowledge of the solar system breakdown, how such a tilt occurs, except through precession. Ben and Dr. Vogt are wrong, at any rate, about the micronova.

❖ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332316290_Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_could_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formation_of_Chillicothe_and_Newark_Earthworks

❖ https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction

❖ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

❖ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything
https://www.academia.edu/53139271/Strong_Letter_Response_to_Mr_Ben_Davidson_Suspicious_Observers_et_al

²⁴ He uses a pejorative sounding voice for the generic unnamed skeptic of his theory each time, it's worth noting for body language purposes.

²⁵ Beaming large, sitting up straight as he is excited about this point, for some reason?

36. 10:27 Jimmy, "Well keep in mind the outer ring would have been water. So that wouldn't necessarily have counted... but some people say this is too big according to Plato's description. ... Well hold on a second, I don't think we should consider that... because of the loss of translation... that we should consider the measurements a key detail."
37. 10:43 Jimmy, "The question becomes 'is it big enough to be a city with possibly millions of people. The way it was described was to be a city busy all day, all night, rich in trade, with languages spoken from all over.... That would imply millions of people.'"
38. 11:08 Jimmy, "If this was indeed a site of an ancient civilization... I mean they would obviously they're not gonna have skyscrapers, so it would have to be an area big enough to sustain that many people and the Richat structure certainly does (sic)."
39. 11:22 Joe, "That this would lead out to the ocean and that these circles would be where the water is? And the ridges would be where the structures are... the houses and the buildings?"
40. 11:33 Jimmy, "And people would say 'where's that stuff now?' And would say 'look at it, it got obliterated.'"
41. 11:38 Joe, "Those people should shut the fuck up (sic). Cause if you look at what's going on with the sand and the clear water erosion marks in the sand... but that also could be wind, right?"
42. 12:04 Jimmy, "Can you scroll in right there? Cause that will show you the ripples more... so it's a combination of sand and rock... that's what I'm talking about, those are giant ripples. And let me just say I'm quoting Randall Carlson who I consider to be an expert on these .. .on geological formations and so... yeah..." (sic)
43. 12:25 Joe, "Right... but isn't that what wind driven sand looks like? If you go to dunes, dunes look like that. ... this is what it would look like, rock and wind driven sand beneath it."
44. 12:39 Jimmy, "So the implication is that it was blasted by water and then *after that* the wind has done its thing..."²⁶
45. 12:48 Joe, "So 20k years ago this was all green lush forest? 5,000!? Really? When do they think Atlantis was?"
46. 12:57 Jimmy, "11,600 is allegedly when it was destroyed, which here's the Younger Dryas climate catastrophe. Technically ... so Plato... this was 600 BC and Plato said it was 9000 years earlier... which coincides with the Younger Dryas climate catastrophe."
47. 13:15 Jimmy, "Which makes it so compelling to me that is... actual scientific evidence that indicates Atlantis actually existed. So because it's very specific"²⁷
48. 13:22 Joe, "Well sort of.. It is very specific but it's not scientific, right? Like, there's no real evidence."
49. 13:33 Jimmy, "Okay let me rephrase... a civilization got ... fucked (sic) 11,600 ... never mind Atlantis... let me rephrase, a civilization was around ... the stories were passed down and they got obliterated."²⁸ That's what I'm implying."
50. 13:45 Joe, "We definitely know that the Younger Dryas Impact Theory is extremely plausible. There are without a doubt... like many many impact points on the Earth where they find this trinitite, this nuclear glass... which you can get from a nuclear explosion, or some sort of meteor act, large scale... all over the continent. We know all over the planet, I should say. We know that that happened. This is like real hardcore geological evidence."
51. 14:18 Joe, "So if we know there were structures before that, which we do now, because Gobekli Tepe and a few other places, that they're reasonably sure were pre 11kya, 12kya, then we know that

²⁶ Jimmy has an unconvinced face at 12:46, not sure what about.

²⁷ A rare a priori fallacy combining with a complete and utter non-sequitur. The funniest thing to me, is the body language is so very endearingly scholarly, left hand poised and blossoming at 13:20 as the crescendo of his mistake comes together. I don't mean to be mean. But what follows is Joe's succinct rebuttal.

²⁸ No, Jimmy, you're implying the Richat is Atlantis. We are inferring that the civilization was obliterated, but you haven't identified a single vector. The megatsunami, by your own admission, came after 5000 years ago (according to your understanding of desertification of the Sahara)

something was around back then that was reasonably sophisticated. How sophisticated, we don't know."

Figure 1 - Atlantis as maintained in our cultural memory: advanced but made of stoe, potentially energized, and with concentric canals of water; credit: Assassin's Creed²⁹

Figure 2 - Also Atlantis as we remember it: sunken in water, and yet somehow still alive; credit: voidswrath.com³⁰

²⁹ <https://assassinscreed.fandom.com/wiki/Atlantis>

³⁰ <https://www.scienceabc.com/eyeopeners/is-the-sunken-city-of-atlantis-real.html>

Responses and Rebuttals

1. I think what Joe Rogan is trying to say is that soil samples of the Earth's crust show a remarkable series of black mat layers, nanodiamonds, "nuclear glass", and other unexplained phenomena. In particular, the YDE is associated with crypto explosive evidence, which he is fast-tracking to YDIT confirmation. The problem with this is that he does not know about Perattian Thunderbolts, whose energy *starts* at 15x the power of a hydrogen bomb, for a **single pulse**. Energetic levels are described in the footnote citations for footnote 21, particularly the first Megafauna paper, Part 4, and Addendum 1, which cites Dr. Peratt's work (only 1 order of magnitude different from my calculations using Maxwell's equations). Gold's work is 3 orders of magnitude stronger than Peratt. The point is, that while we know it is not caused by terrestrial lightning, the greatest weight of evidence is for a Step Potential + Climate Change + *some impactors*, like the Greenland Strike + megatsunamis (also covered in Part 3 of Addendum 1). Bear in mind the myths of the natives of the world specify the thunderbolts and thunderbirds. The majority of "stones" were thrown by Zeus later, as well as with these thunderbolts. However, as I reveal in Addendum 2, the greater evidence - as we advanced the research of giants of Electric, Plasma, and allstream catastrophic-diffusionism history in the 20th century, is that the Chinese, Egyptians, Zoroastrians, Mayans, Hindus, and the world were correct: our previous star

Shamash/Amun-Ra/Kronos/Anu died:

- a. It bifurcated into Jupiter and proto-Saturn (Enlil/Zeus and Enki/Hera, respectively)
- b. Enki fairly quickly birthed Neptune, which was in a strongly electrical state (Poseidon), which was temporarily our Lord (Shiva).
 - i. Its electrical misbehaviors were stilled by Jupiter and Saturn via discharge, as evidenced in the Ramayana
- c. Venus/Athena was pulled out of Saturn, and the refuse formed the "diadem" of Osiris, and it is made of water.
- d. We circulated the triple God until the system entered a LaGrange arrangement that made a "tree of life" or "world's tree" of plasma. This arrangement was relatively stable for a few thousand years.
- e. The system later broke down due to unknown causes, probably the introduction of Hades/planet Uranus,, coming with the approaching Sol/Apollo (our new sun)
- f. The Egyptians still revered the old God/sun as "superior", and potentially Saturn (Osiris) remained a polar lord for some time. But when we touched Enki's "left side" there was a Deluge and that era ended.³¹
- g. Venus and Mars coming nearby instigated various other issues, and all of this had major effects upon religion and human development, such as government, divine right to rule, plunder economics/war, and cosmological paranoia and obsession.

As for Joe's assertion that it's a fact, unfortunately, it is not.

2. We're making some assumptions here about these cultures. Firstly, let's be clear that there is **0 present evidence for a specific city called Atlantis**, there are only strong indicators. I covered all of this and "what we know" in "Unboxing Atlantis." Chances are, it was the Azores, which is safe to say we haven't explored because of a) depth and b) cost. However, there's also no indication that civilization being advanced back then meant anything more than:
 - a. Seafaring
 - b. Potentially intercontinental
 - c. Maybe correlated or related to advanced stone work

³¹ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1QnRXGf1kju3C_CZX06njKK-tnrbGGjg5kOGkRAI-zSM/edit?usp=sharing

We have some of the drawings about the event also from Columbia, and the “Paracan” lines in Peru, as well as dating from Tiahuanaco, but nothing is definitive. What is clear, though, is that the Tepe Period is a reaction to stimulus, not the cause of it.

Figure 3 - Shamash’s diameter ratio increases to nearly 2.0 (Lexington earthwork was 1.78), explosions indicated to birth Jupiter; anode tufting and Z-banding clearly visible; notice also the synchrotron formation at right and the birth of Neptune near star; dots are anode tufting; credit: J Denzer

If Atlanteans were using the Great Pyramid (with Bauval’s plausible dating, as per my calculations⁴¹) to connect to the Earth’s Van Allen Currents (as per Chris Dunn’s power plant hypothesis and Kristian Birkeland’s auroral plasma research⁴²), and they experienced an explosion in the King’s Chamber due to electrical overload, that is a far cry from proving that they caused their island to sink beneath the waves. More likely the Azores collapsed due to crustal buckling, and them (and other sunken lands) being near rifts and faults. We do know this is possible because a city like Dwarka was found beneath the water, and it dates from the Venutian event, 4400-5500 BP. But that type of destruction, or that of Sodom which has allegedly been found, are **not** the kind of collapse or destruction we expect from sudden rift changes and crustal buckling due to passing electrodynamic forces, which far exceed the power of gravity.

4. I agree with Joe, it is causing an awakening. I hope he reads my “On the Origins of Religions”⁴³ and “Unboxing Atlantis” as well as the “Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky”⁴⁴ so he can begin to understand the kind of forces which can extinguish large animals, but spare the world, be selective but widely destructive, and quickly cool and quickly heat the world, causing massive desertification. The vector for transmutation, as well as the origins of extra sand. Comets do not solve these issues.

⁴¹ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final

⁴² As per Dr. Peratt, K. Birkeland was researching Giza as his terella’s showed currents at 30 degrees N.

⁴³ https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

⁴⁴

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

5. There is no evidence for this. There is solid evidence for Archaic and Megalithic diffusion "doing great things." We should be careful to distinguish what we want with what is currently known.
6. We are going to post entirely what was said by Plato, of Solon's words, of the Egyptian priest, and then we can dispense with any guesswork or additional Atlantis lore/myth from later speculators.

"Plato has preserved for us the history of Atlantis. If our views are correct, it is one of the most valuable records which have come down to us from antiquity. Plato lived 400 years before the birth of Christ. His ancestor, Solon, was the great law-giver of Athens 600 years before the Christian era. Solon visited Egypt.

Plutarch says, "Solon attempted in verse a large description, or rather fabulous account of the Atlantic Island, which he had learned from the wise men of Sais, and which particularly concerned the Athenians; but by reason of his age, not want of leisure (as Plato would have it), he was apprehensive the work would be too much for him, and therefore did not go through with it.

These verses are a proof that business was not the hinderance: "'I grow in learning as I grow in age.' And again: "'Wine, wit, and beauty still their charms bestow, Light all the shades of life, and cheer us as we go.' "Plato, ambitious to cultivate and adorn the subject of the Atlantic Island, as a delightful spot in some fair field unoccupied, to which also he had some claim by reason of his being related to Solon, laid out magnificent courts and enclosures, and erected a grand entrance to it, such as no other story, fable, or Poem ever had. But, as he began it late, he ended his life before the work, so that the more the reader is delighted with the part that is written, the more regret he has to find it unfinished." There can be no question that Solon visited Egypt. The causes of his departure from Athens, for a period of ten years, are fully explained by Plutarch.

He dwelt, he tells us, "On the Canopian shore, by Nile's deep mouth." There he conversed upon points of philosophy and history with the most learned of the Egyptian priests. He was a man of extraordinary force and penetration of mind, as his laws and his sayings, which have been preserved to us, testify. There is no improbability in the statement that he commenced in verse a history and description of Atlantis, which he left unfinished at his death; and it requires no great stretch of the imagination to believe that this manuscript reached the hands of his successor and descendant, Plato; a scholar, thinker, and historian like himself, and, like himself, one of the profoundest minds of the ancient world.

The Egyptian priest had said to Solon, "You have no antiquity of history, and no history of antiquity;" and Solon doubtless realized fully the vast importance of a record which carried human history back, not only thousands of years before the era of Greek civilization, but many thousands of years before even the establishment of the kingdom of Egypt; and he was anxious to preserve for his half-civilized countrymen this inestimable record of the past. Critias: Then listen, Socrates, to a strange tale, which is, however, certainly true, as Solon, who was the wisest of the seven sages, declared. He was a relative and great friend of my great-grandfather, Dropidas, as he himself says in several of his poems; and Dropidas told Critias, my grandfather, who remembered, and told us, that there were of old great and marvelous actions of the Athenians, which have passed into oblivion through time and the destruction of the human race and one in particular, which was the greatest of them all, the recital of which will be a suitable testimony of our gratitude to you....

Socrates: Very good; and what is this ancient famous action of which Critias spoke, not as a mere legend, but as a veritable action of the Athenian State, which Solon recounted! Critias: I will tell an old-world story which I heard from an aged man; for Critias (the elder) was, as he said, at that time nearly ninety years of age, and I was about ten years of age. Now the day was that day of the Apaturia which is called the registration of youth; at which, according to custom, our parents gave prizes for recitations, and the poems of several poets were recited by us boys, and many of us sung the poems of Solon, which were new at the time. One of our tribe, either because this was his real opinion, or because he thought that he would please Critias, said that, in his judgment, Solon was not only the

wisest of men but the noblest of poets.

The old man, I well remember, brightened up at this, and said, smiling: "Yes, Amynander, if Solon had only, like other poets, made poetry the business of his life, and had completed the tale which he brought with him from Egypt, and had not been compelled, by reason of the factions and troubles which he found stirring in this country when he came home, to attend to other matters, in my opinion he would have been as famous as Homer, or Hesiod, or any poet."

"And what was that poem about, Critias?" said the person who addressed him. "About the greatest action which the Athenians ever did, and which ought to have been most famous, but which, through the lapse of time and the destruction of the actors, has not come down to us."

"Tell us," said the other, "the whole story, and how and from whom Solon heard this veritable tradition."

He replied: "At the head of the Egyptian Delta, where the river Nile divides, there is a certain district which is called the district of Sais, and the great city of the district is also called Sais, and is the city from which Amasis the king was sprung. And the citizens have a deity who is their foundress: she is called in the Egyptian tongue Neith, which is asserted by them to be the same whom the Hellenes called Athene (Athena). Now, the citizens of this city are great lovers of the Athenians, and say that they are in some way related to them. Thither came Solon, who was received by them with great honor; and he asked the priests, who were most skilful in such matters, about antiquity, and made the discovery that neither he nor any other Hellene knew anything worth mentioning about the times of old. On one occasion, when he was drawing them on to speak of antiquity, he began to tell about the most ancient things in our part of the world--about Phoroneus, who is called 'the first,' and about Niobe; and, after the Deluge, to tell of the lives of Deucalion and Pyrrha; and he traced the genealogy of their descendants, and attempted to reckon how many years old were the events of which he was speaking, and to give the dates. Thereupon, one of the priests, who was of very great age; said, 'O Solon, Solon, you Hellenes are but children, and there is never an old man who is an Hellene.'

Solon, hearing this, said, 'What do you mean?'

'I mean to say,' he replied, 'that in mind you are all young; there is no old opinion handed down among you by ancient tradition, nor any science which is hoary with age. And I will tell you the reason of this: there have been, and there will be again, many destructions of mankind arising out of many causes. There is a story which even you have preserved, that once upon a time Phaethon, the son of Helios, having yoked the steeds in his father's chariot, because he was not able to drive them in the path of his father, burnt up all that was upon the earth, and was himself destroyed by a thunderbolt. Now, this has the form of a myth, but really signifies a declination of the bodies moving around the earth and in the heavens, and a great conflagration of things upon the earth recurring at long intervals of time: when this happens, those who live upon the mountains and in dry and lofty places are more liable to destruction than those who dwell by rivers or on the sea-shore; and from this calamity the Nile, who is our never-failing savior, saves and delivers us. When, on the other hand, the gods purge the earth with a deluge of water, among you herdsmen and shepherds on the mountains are the survivors, whereas those of you who live in cities are carried by the rivers into the sea; but in this country neither at that time nor at any other does the water come from above on the fields, having always a tendency to come up from below, for which reason the things preserved here are said to be the oldest. The fact is, that wherever the extremity of winter frost or of summer sun does not prevent, the human race is always increasing at times, and at other times diminishing in numbers. And whatever happened either in your country or in ours, or in any other region of which we are informed--if any action which is noble or great, or in any other way remarkable has taken place, all that has been written down of old, and is preserved in our temples; whereas you and other nations are just being provided with letters and the other things which States require; and then, at the usual period, the stream from heaven descends like a pestilence, and leaves only those of you who are destitute of letters and education; and thus you

have to begin all over again as children, and know nothing of what happened in ancient times, either among us or among yourselves. As for those genealogies of yours which you have recounted to us, Solon, they are no better than the tales of children; for, in the first place, you remember one deluge only, whereas there were many of them; and, in the next place, you do not know that there dwelt in your land the fairest and noblest race of men which ever lived, of whom you and your whole city are but a seed or remnant. And this was unknown to you, because for many generations the survivors of that destruction died and made no sign. For there was a time, Solon, before that great deluge of all, when the city which now is Athens was first in war, and was preeminent for the excellence of her laws, and is said to have performed the noblest deeds, and to have had the fairest constitution of any of which tradition tells, under the face of heaven.'

Solon marveled at this, and earnestly requested the priest to inform him exactly and in order about these former citizens. 'You are welcome to hear about them, Solon,' said the priest, 'both for your own sake and for that of the city; and, above all, for the sake of the goddess who is the common patron and protector and educator of both our cities. She founded your city a thousand years before ours, receiving from the Earth and Hephaestus the seed of your race, and then she founded ours, the constitution of which is set down in our sacred registers as 8000 years old. As touching the citizens of 9000 years ago, I will briefly inform you of their laws and of the noblest of their actions; and the exact particulars of the whole we will hereafter go through at our leisure in the sacred registers themselves. If you compare these very laws with your own, you will find that many of ours are the counterpart of yours, as they were in the olden time. In the first place, there is the caste of priests, which is separated from all the others; next there are the artificers, who exercise their several crafts by themselves, and without admixture of any other; and also there is the class of shepherds and that of hunters, as well as that of husbandmen; and you will observe, too, that the warriors in Egypt are separated from all the other classes, and are commanded by the law only to engage in war; moreover, the weapons with which they are equipped are shields and spears, and this the goddess taught first among you, and then in Asiatic countries, and we among the Asiatics first adopted.

"Then, as to wisdom, do you observe what care the law took from the very first, searching out and comprehending the whole order of things down to prophecy and medicine, the latter with a view to health; and out of these divine elements drawing what was needful for human life, and adding every sort of knowledge which was connected with them. All this order and arrangement the goddess first imparted to you when establishing your city; and she chose the spot of earth in which you were born, because she saw that the happy temperament of the seasons in that land would produce the wisest of men. Wherefore the goddess, who was a lover both of war and of wisdom, selected, and first of all settled that spot which was the most likely to produce men likest herself. And there you dwelt, having such laws as these and still better ones, and excelled all mankind in all virtue, as became the children and disciples of the gods. Many great and wonderful deeds are recorded of your State in our histories; but one of them exceeds all the rest in greatness and valor; for these histories tell of a mighty power which was aggressing wantonly against the whole of Europe and Asia, and to which your city put an end. This power came forth out of the Atlantic Ocean, for in those days the Atlantic was navigable; and there was an island situated in front of the straits which you call the Columns of Heracles (the Strait of Gibraltar, known as the Pillars of Hercules): the island was larger than Libya and Asia (Turkey) put together, and was the way to other islands, and from the islands you might pass through the whole of the opposite continent which surrounded the true ocean; for this sea which is within the Straits of Heracles is only a harbor, having a narrow entrance, but that other is a real sea, and the surrounding land may be most truly called a continent.

Now, in the island of Atlantis there was a great and wonderful empire, which had rule over the whole island and several others, as well as over parts of the continent; and, besides these, they subjected the parts of Libya within the Columns of Heracles as far as Egypt, and of Europe as far as

Tyrrhenia (Italy). The vast power thus gathered into one, endeavored to subdue at one blow our country and yours, and the whole of the land which was within the straits; and then, Solon, your country shone forth, in the excellence of her virtue and strength, among all mankind; for she was the first in courage and military skill, and was the leader of the Hellenes.

And when the rest fell off from her, being compelled to stand alone, after having undergone the very extremity of danger, she defeated and triumphed over the invaders, and preserved from slavery those who were not yet subjected, and freely liberated all the others who dwelt within the limits of Heracles. But afterward there occurred violent earthquakes and floods, and in a single day and night of rain all your warlike men in a body sunk into the earth, and the island of Atlantis in like manner disappeared, and was sunk beneath the sea. And that is the reason why the sea in those parts is impassable and impenetrable, because there is such a quantity of shallow mud in the way; and this was caused by the subsidence of the island. [end excerpt]⁴⁵

"But in addition to the gods whom you have mentioned, I would specially invoke Mnemosyne; for all the important part of what I have to tell is dependent on her favor, and if I can recollect and recite enough of what was said by the priests, and brought hither by Solon, I doubt not that I shall satisfy the requirements of this theatre. To that task, then, I will at once address myself.

"Let me begin by observing, first of all, that nine thousand was the sum of years which had elapsed since the war which was said to have taken place between all those who dwelt outside the Pillars of Heracles and those who dwelt within them: this war I am now to describe. Of the combatants on the one side the city of Athens was reported to have been the ruler, and to have directed the contest; the combatants on the other side were led by the kings of the islands of Atlantis, which, as I was saying, once had an extent greater than that of Libya and Asia (Turkey); and, when afterward sunk by an earthquake, became an impassable barrier of mud to voyagers sailing from hence to the ocean. The progress of the history will unfold the various tribes of barbarians and Hellenes which then existed, as they successively appear on the scene; but I must begin by describing, first of all, the Athenians as they were in that day, and their enemies who fought with them; and I shall have to tell of the power and form of government of both of them. Let us give the precedence to Athens. . . . (omitted?)

"Many great deluges have taken place during the nine thousand years, for that is the number of years which have elapsed since the time of which I am speaking; and in all the ages and changes of things there has never been any sediment of the earth flowing down from the mountains, as in other places, which is worth speaking of. It has always been carried round in a circle, and disappeared in the depths below. The consequence is that, in comparison of what then was, there are remaining in small islets only the bones of the wasted body, as they may be called, all the richer and softer parts of the soil having fallen away, and the mere skeleton of the country being left. . . .

"And next, if I have not forgotten what I heard when I was a child, I will impart to you the character and origin of their adversaries (the Atlanteans); for friends should not keep their stories to themselves, but have them in common. Yet, before proceeding farther in the narrative, I ought to warn you that you must not be surprised if you should hear Hellenic names given to foreigners. I will tell you the reason of this: Solon, who was intending to use the tale for his poem, made an investigation into the meaning of the names, and found that the early Egyptians, in writing them down, had translated them into their own language, and he recovered the meaning of the several names and retranslated them, and copied them out again in our language. My great-grandfather, Dropidas, had the original writing, which is still in my possession, and was carefully studied by me when I was a child. Therefore, if you

⁴⁵ Excerpt from "Critias" by Plato c.428 - c.347 BC from "The Antediluvian World" by Ignatius Donnelly <https://ascendingpassage.com/plato-atlantis-critias.htm>

hear names such as are used in this country, you must not be surprised, for I have told you the reason of them.

Platos' city of Atlantis

"The tale, which was of great length, began as follows: I have before remarked, in speaking of the allotments of the gods, that they distributed the whole earth into portions differing in extent, and made themselves temples and sacrifices.

And Poseidon, receiving for his lot the island of Atlantis, begat children by a mortal woman, and settled them in a part of the island which I will proceed to describe. On the side toward the sea, and in the center of the whole island, there was a plain which is said to have been the fairest of all plains, and very fertile.

Near the plain again, and also in the center of the island, at a distance of about fifty stadia (one stadia=606 feet), there was a mountain, not very high on any side. In this mountain there dwelt one of the earth-born primeval men of that country, whose name was Evenor, and he had a wife named Leucippe, and they had an only daughter, who was named Cleito. The maiden was growing up to womanhood when her father and mother died.

Poseidon fell in love with her, and had intercourse with her; and, breaking the ground, enclosed the hill in which she dwelt all round, making alternate zones of sea and land, larger and smaller, encircling one another; there were two of land and three of water, which he turned as with a lathe out of the center of the island, equidistant every way, so that no man could get to the island, for ships and voyages were not yet heard of. He himself, as he was a god, found no difficulty in making special arrangements for the center island, bringing two streams of water under the earth, which he caused to ascend as springs, one of warm water and the other of cold, and making every variety of food to spring up abundantly in the earth. He also begat and brought up five pairs of male children, dividing the island of Atlantis into ten portions: he gave to the first-born of the eldest pair his mother's dwelling and the surrounding allotment, which was the largest and best, and made him king over the rest; the others he made princes, and gave them rule over many men and a large territory.

And he named them all: the eldest, who was king, he named Atlas, and from him the whole island and the ocean received the name of Atlantic. To his twin-brother, who was born after him, and obtained as his lot the extremity of the island toward the Pillars of Heracles, as far as the country which is still called the region of Gades in that part of the world, he gave the name which in the Hellenic language is Eumelus, in the language of the country which is named after him, Gadeirus. Of the second pair of twins, he called one Ampheres and the other Evaemon. To the third pair of twins he gave the name Mneseus to the elder, and Autochthon to the one who followed him. Of the fourth pair of twins he called the elder Elasippus and the younger Mestor, And of the fifth pair he gave to the elder the name of Azaes, and to the younger Diaprepes.

All these and their descendants were the inhabitants and rulers of divers islands in the open sea; and also, as has been already said, they held sway in the other direction over the country within the Pillars as far as Egypt and Tyrrhenia (Italy). Now Atlas had a numerous and honorable family, and his eldest branch always retained the kingdom, which the eldest son handed on to his eldest for many generations; and they had such an amount of wealth as was never before possessed by kings and potentates, and is not likely ever to be again, and they were furnished with everything which they could have, both in city and country. For, because of the greatness of their empire, many things were brought to them from foreign countries, and the island itself provided much of what was required by them for the uses of life. In the first place, they dug out of the earth whatever was to be found there, mineral as well as metal, and that which is now only a name, and was then something more than a name -- orichalcum -- was dug out of the earth in many parts of the island, and, with the exception of gold, was esteemed the most precious of metals among the men of those days. There was an abundance of wood for

carpenters' work, and sufficient maintenance for tame and wild animals. Moreover, there were a great number of elephants in the island, and there was provision for animals of every kind, both for those which live in lakes and marshes and rivers, and also for those which live in mountains and on plains, and therefore for the animal which is the largest and most voracious of them.

Also, whatever fragrant things there are in the earth, whether roots, or herbage, or woods, or distilling drops of flowers or fruits, grew and thrived in that land; and again, the cultivated fruit of the earth, both the dry edible fruit and other species of food, which we call by the general name of legumes, and the fruits having a hard rind, affording drinks, and meats, and ointments, and good store of chestnuts and the like, which may be used to play with, and are fruits which spoil with keeping--and the pleasant kinds of dessert which console us after dinner, when we are full and tired of eating--all these that sacred island lying beneath the sun brought forth fair and wondrous in infinite abundance.

All these things they received from the earth, and they employed themselves in constructing their temples, and palaces, and harbors, and docks; and they arranged the whole country in the following manner: First of all they bridged over the zones of sea which surrounded the ancient metropolis, and made a passage into and out of the royal palace; they began to build the palace and then the habitation of the god and of their ancestors.

This they continued to ornament in successive generations, every king surpassing the one who came before him to the utmost of his power, until they made the building a marvel to behold for size and for beauty. And, beginning from the sea, they dug a canal three hundred feet in width and one hundred feet in depth, and fifty stadia in length, which they carried through to the outermost zone, making a passage from the sea up to this, which became a harbor, and leaving an opening sufficient to enable the largest vessels to find ingress.

Moreover, they divided the zones of land which parted the zones of sea, constructing bridges of such a width as would leave a passage for a single trireme to pass out of one into another, and roofed them over; and there was a way underneath for the ships, for the banks of the zones were raised considerably above the water. Now the largest of the zones into which a passage was cut from the sea was three stadia in breadth, and the zone of land which came next of equal breadth; but the next two, as well the zone of water as of land, were two stadia, and the one which surrounded the central island was a stadium only in width.

The island in which the palace was situated had a diameter of five stadia. This, and the zones and the bridge, which was the sixth part of a stadium in width, they surrounded by a stone wall, on either side placing towers, and gates on the bridges where the sea passed in. The stone which was used in the work they quarried from underneath the center island and from underneath the zones, on the outer as well as the inner side. One kind of stone was white, another black, and a third red; and, as they quarried, they at the same time hollowed out docks double within, having roofs formed out of the native rock.

Some of their buildings were simple, but in others they put together different stones, which they intermingled for the sake of ornament, to be a natural source of delight. The entire circuit of the wall which went round the outermost one they covered with a coating of brass, and the circuit of the next wall they coated with tin, and the third, which encompassed the citadel flashed with the red light of orichalcum.

The palaces in the interior of the citadel were constructed in this wise: In the center was a holy temple dedicated to Cleito and Poseidon, which remained inaccessible, and was surrounded by an enclosure of gold; this was the spot in which they originally begat the race of the ten princes, and thither they annually brought the fruits of the earth in their season from all the ten portions, and performed sacrifices to each of them. Here, too, was Poseidon's own temple, of a stadium in length and half a stadium in width, and of a proportionate height, having a sort of barbaric splendor. All the outside of the temple, with the exception of the pinnacles, they covered with silver, and the pinnacles with gold. In the

interior of the temple the roof was of ivory, adorned everywhere with gold and silver and orichalcum; all the other parts of the walls and pillars and floor they lined with orichalcum.

In the temple they placed statues of gold: there was the god himself standing in a chariot--the charioteer of six winged horses--and of such a size that he touched the roof of the building with his head; around him there were a hundred Nereids riding on dolphins, for such was thought to be the number of them in that day. There were also in the interior of the temple other images which had been dedicated by private individuals.

And around the temple on the outside were placed statues of gold of all the ten kings and of their wives; and there were many other great offerings, both of kings and of private individuals, coming both from the city itself and the foreign cities over which they held sway. There was an altar, too, which in size and workmanship corresponded to the rest of the work, and there were palaces in like manner which answered to the greatness of the kingdom and the glory of the temple. "In the next place, they used fountains both of cold and hot springs; these were very abundant, and both kinds wonderfully adapted to use by reason of the sweetness and excellence of their waters.

They constructed buildings about them, and planted suitable trees; also cisterns, some open to the heaven, other which they roofed over, to be used in winter as warm baths, there were the king's baths, and the baths of private persons, which were kept apart; also separate baths for women, and others again for horses and cattle, and to them they gave as much adornment as was suitable for them. The water which ran off they carried, some to the grove of Poseidon, where were growing all manner of trees of wonderful height and beauty, owing to the excellence of the soil; the remainder was conveyed by aqueducts which passed over the bridges to the outer circles: and there were many temples built and dedicated to many gods; also gardens and places of exercise, some for men, and some set apart for horses, in both of the two islands formed by the zones; and in the centre of the larger of the two there was a race-course of a stadium in width, and in length allowed to extend all round the island, for horses to race in.

Also there were guard-houses at intervals for the body-guard, the more trusted of whom had their duties appointed to them in the lesser zone, which was nearer the Acropolis; while the most trusted of all had houses given them within the citadel, and about the persons of the kings. The docks were full of triremes and naval stores, and all things were quite ready for use. Enough of the plan of the royal palace.

Crossing the outer harbors, which were three in number, you would come to a wall which began at the sea and went all round: this was everywhere distant fifty stadia from the largest zone and harbor, and enclosed the whole, meeting at the mouth of the channel toward the sea. The entire area was densely crowded with habitations; and the canal and the largest of the harbors were full of vessels and merchants coming from all parts, who, from their numbers, kept up a multitudinous sound of human voices and din of all sorts night and day. I have repeated his descriptions of the city and the parts about the ancient palace nearly as he gave them, and now I must endeavor to describe the nature and arrangement of the rest of the country.

The whole country was described as being very lofty and precipitous on the side of the sea, but the country immediately about and surrounding the city was a level plain, itself surrounded by mountains which descended toward the sea; it was smooth and even, but of an oblong shape, extending in one direction three thousand stadia⁴⁶, and going up the country from the sea through the centre of the island two thousand stadia; the whole region of the island lies toward the south, and is sheltered from the north. The surrounding mountains he celebrated for their number and size and beauty, in which they exceeded all that are now to be seen anywhere; having in them also many

⁴⁶ The stade consisted of 625 Roman feet (185 metres or 606.9 feet), or 125 paces, and was equal to one-eighth of a mile. <https://www.britannica.com/science/stade-measurement>

>>Therefore 3,000 stadia = 344.9 miles; 2000 stadia ~ 230 miles <<

wealthy inhabited villages, and rivers and lakes, and meadows supplying food enough for every animal, wild or tame, and wood of various sorts, abundant for every kind of work.

I will now describe the plain, which had been cultivated during many ages by many generations of kings. It was rectangular, and for the most part straight and oblong; and what it wanted of the straight line followed the line of the circular ditch. The depth and width and length of this ditch were incredible and gave the impression that such a work, in addition to so many other works, could hardly have been wrought by the hand of man. But I must say what I have heard.

It was excavated to the depth of a hundred feet, and its breadth was a stadium everywhere; it was carried round the whole of the plain, and was ten thousand stadia in length⁴⁷. It received the streams which came down from the mountains, and winding round the plain, and touching the city at various points, was there let off into the sea.

From above, likewise, straight canals of a hundred feet in width were cut in the plain, and again let off into the ditch, toward the sea; these canals were at intervals of a hundred stadia, and by them they brought down the wood from the mountains to the city, and conveyed the fruits of the earth in ships, cutting transverse passages from one canal into another, and to the city. Twice in the year they gathered the fruits of the earth--in winter having the benefit of the rains, and in summer introducing the water of the canals.

As to the population, each of the lots in the plain had an appointed chief of men who were fit for military service, and the size of the lot was to be a square of ten stadia each way, and the total number of all the lots was sixty thousand.

"And of the inhabitants of the mountains and of the rest of the country there was also a vast multitude having leaders, to whom they were assigned according to their dwellings and villages. The leader was required to furnish for the war the sixth portion of a war-chariot, so as to make up a total of ten thousand chariots; also two horses and riders upon them, and a light chariot without a seat, accompanied by a fighting man on foot carrying a small shield, and having a charioteer mounted to guide the horses; also, he was bound to furnish two heavy-armed men, two archers, two slingers, three stone-shooters, and three javelin men, who were skirmishers, and four sailors to make up a complement of twelve hundred ships.

Such was the order of war in the royal city--that of the other nine governments was different in each of them, and would be wearisome to narrate. As to offices and honors, the following was the arrangement from the first: Each of the ten kings, in his own division and in his own city, had the absolute control of the citizens, and in many cases of the laws, punishing and slaying whomsoever he would.

"Now the relations of their governments to one another were regulated by the injunctions of Poseidon as the law had handed them down. These were inscribed by the first men on a column of orichalcum, which was situated in the middle of the island, at the temple of Poseidon, whither the people were gathered together every fifth and sixth years alternately, thus giving equal honor to the odd and to the even number.

And when they were gathered together they consulted about public affairs, and inquired if any one had transgressed in anything, and passed judgment on him accordingly--and before they passed judgment they gave their pledges to one another in this wise: There were bulls who had the range of the temple of Poseidon; and the ten who were left alone in the temple, after they had offered prayers to the gods that they might take the sacrifices which were acceptable to them, hunted the bulls without weapons, but with staves and nooses; and the bull which they caught they led up to the column; the victim was then struck on the head by them, and slain over the sacred inscription. Now on the column, besides the law, there was inscribed an oath invoking mighty curses on the disobedient. When, therefore, after offering sacrifice according to their customs, they had burnt the limbs of the bull, they

⁴⁷ 1147 miles; not an easy size to find in any potential theory

mingled a cup and cast in a clot of blood for each of them; the rest of the victim they took to the fire, after having made a purification of the column all round.

Then they drew from the cup in golden vessels, and, pouring a libation on the fire, they swore that they would judge according to the laws on the column, and would punish any one who had previously transgressed, and that for the future they would not, if they could help, transgress any of the inscriptions, and would not command or obey any ruler who commanded them to act otherwise than according to the laws of their father Poseidon.

This was the prayer which each of them offered up for himself and for his family, at the same time drinking, and dedicating the vessel in the temple of the god; and, after spending some necessary time at supper, when darkness came on and the fire about the sacrifice was cool, all of them put on most beautiful azure robes, and, sitting on the ground at night near the embers of the sacrifices on which they had sworn, and extinguishing all the fire about the temple, they received and gave judgment, if any of them had any accusation to bring against any one; and, when they had given judgment, at daybreak they wrote down their sentences on a golden tablet, and deposited them as memorials with their robes.

There were many special laws which the several kings had inscribed about the temples, but the most important was the following: That they were not to take up arms against one another, and they were all to come to the rescue if any one in any city attempted to overthrow the royal house. Like their ancestors, they were to deliberate in common about war and other matters, giving the supremacy to the family of Atlas; and the king was not to have the power of life and death over any of his kinsmen, unless he had the assent of the majority of the ten kings.

"Such was the vast power which the god settled in the lost island of Atlantis; and this he afterward directed against our land on the following pretext, as traditions tell: For many generations, as long as the divine nature lasted in them, they were obedient to the laws, and well-affectioned toward the gods, who were their kinsmen; for they possessed true and in every way great spirits, practicing gentleness and wisdom in the various chances of life, and in their intercourse with one another. They despised everything but virtue, not caring for their present state of life, and thinking lightly on the possession of gold and other property, which seemed only a burden to them; neither were they intoxicated by luxury; nor did wealth deprive them of their self-control; but they were sober, and saw clearly that all these goods are increased by virtuous friendship with one another, and that by excessive zeal for them, and honor of them, the good of them is lost, and friendship perishes with them.

"By such reflections, and by the continuance in them of a divine nature, all that which we have described waxed and increased in them; but when this divine portion began to fade away in them, and became diluted too often, and with too much of the mortal admixture, and the human nature got the upper-hand, then, they being unable to bear their fortune, became unseemly.

To him who had an eye to see, they began to appear base, and had lost the fairest of their precious gifts; but to those who had no eye to see the true happiness, they still appeared glorious and blessed at the very time when they were filled with unrighteous avarice and power.

Zeus, the god of gods, who rules with law, and is able to see into such things, perceiving that an honorable race was in a most wretched state, and wanting to inflict punishment on them, that they might be chastened and improved, collected all the gods into his most holy habitation, which, being placed in the center of the world, sees all things that partake of generation. And when he had called them together he spake as follows: "[Here Plato's story abruptly ends. You get the image of this wise old bearded man taking a break to work out the words that Zeus would speak, and never coming back to it...]⁴⁸ (emphasis: mine, otherwise sic)

⁴⁸ Excerpt from "Timaeus" by Plato c.428 - c.347 BC
reprinted from "The Antediluvian World" by Ignatius Donnelly <https://ascendingpassage.com/plato-atlantis-timaeus.htm>

7. It's clear from reading Plato's words we can make 3 separate distinctions, which are in no ways contradictory though they are very confusing.
- The tale is semi-historical, meaning that the details, and probably even the meeting with *an* Egyptian authority, happened. The details are too salient to the remainder of EPEMC hypothesis, to be coincidental. It is highly doubtful Plato had access to "Enki and the World Order,"⁴⁹ the "Enuma Elish,"⁵⁰ or the "Atrahasis"⁵¹ texts, unless they are Greek forgeries. Therefore, the data is real, although it will be suspect.
 - Plato's bent on a Philosopher King colours his descriptions of the "Golden Age" and yet there is something candidly compelling about the description. It is over specific (and idealized) and yet there seems to be some legitimate aspect to it. However, given the concentric circle earthworks of Peru and Biggs Site, KY near to the famous Portsmouth OH (defunct) earthworks which resemble Avebury, one cannot help but sense there is a cosmic story here. It could very well be that the Atlanteans built about what they saw in the sky, as a design. But we don't see that at Gobekli Tepe or Gunung Padang. So the author thinks these concentric circles are a mixture of the original tale and that which was recorded as the sun (Sol) made its approach, growing stronger, and creating halos in the plasma dusty of Shamash. This event being seen, became also an Olympian "city in the sky" and the two stories have mingled. The formations seen around the world therefore are recreations of a cosmic, and it's possible or even likely if there were Atlanteans in a city of Atlantis that they were highly organized. But as for the details here 'it will be a matter of faith. If one takes the tale with faith, take the whole tale (with a grain of salt, so to speak.) Or take none of it seriously. In which case Jimmy's later statements about dimensions, to me, make no sense.
 - Whatever one can say about the tale, it must be at least partially fictional. But the most pertinent details are the location and general descriptions, and they make it clear:

The Richat Cannot Be Atlantis, period.⁵²

8. It is a little bit interesting that he comes to this conclusion. The Great Salt Lake, and many salt beds in California, as well as Mono Lake, and places like the Aral Sea in Asia are not in the ocean, and yet have plenty of salt. Moreover the (probably electrically created) Upheaval Dome is in Utah as well, and full of salt. Salt appears to be one of the most important non-precious metal, non-coal remnants of electrical discharge events. Kentucky is full of salt as well, and obviously electrogeological regions proximal to identified features, one of which is a "soda vein" that is clearly electrical. Furthermore, the Hicks Dome, which might be a bolide and airburst site like Melbourne 1491⁵³, has salt remnants as well as the liesegang banding and magnetic anomalies. Nearby to Hicks dome is the world's largest fluorspar deposits. Mineral deposits are common. The Michigan copper deposits are proximal to what is possible to be a large mega arc current from the prehistoric period. Meanwhile salty cenotes in Mexico show self-similarity to lightning mound heaps found in the Arizona desert. At Shiprock, NM, mineral veins for which act as the opposite to lava tubes (they upthrust), and at large cathode sites like Wudang Mountain in China and the Black Hills of North Dakota, we see many types of unique mineral and water behaviors. One should not jump to any conclusions about the origins of the salt without isotopic analysis. Chances are there is ocean salt there from the clear megatsunami fluvial inundation, but there will also be natural salts and potentially unique salts with radioactive signatures, such as at Upheaval Dome.

⁴⁹ <https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/section1/tr113.htm>

⁵⁰ <https://www.sacred-texts.com/ane/enuma.htm>

⁵¹ <https://geha.paginas.ufsc.br/files/2017/04/Atrahasis.pdf>

⁵² It is not outside the strait of Gibraltar and in the Atlantic ocean.

⁵³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dgj393oHQsg>

9. Jimmy has this backwards. There is more proof of Atlantis than there is of spectacular Atlantean civilizations. Whatever I think about the Bosnian half-pyramids and their proto-concrete, or about Gunang Padang's potential library in a volcanic cavern... is irrelevant to the data present. There are no advanced cultures at either site. They are stone age. Without excavations at even Dwarka, let alone the Azores or Bimini Row, there's simply no cause to say Atlanteans were "doing spectacular things."
10. Well they get them from comparative samples and ~190 years of record building, some careful, some pure wild speculation, cobbled together with ego, guesswork, pre-computer "data" analysis, and compared to highly dubious ice and carbon dating, with an incomplete knowledge of nuclear anatomy, electromagnetism, and an almost willful ignorance of plasma and electric behavior (to the point that it's shameful), with the seal of approval of cults of personality in astronomy, spectroscopy, physics, archaeology, and geology. The result is that the oldest stone on Earth's surfaces supposedly 3.8 billion years old in the middle of the North American shelf, but the Earth is 4.5 billion years old according to fake Big Bang cosmology⁵⁴, which says the Universe is 13.8 billion years old although one star⁵⁵ - dated with doppler red shift which has been shown to be wrong⁵⁶ - is older than that⁵⁷. In other words, Jimmy is not wrong, a million years here, or there, *doesn't make much difference*.

However, unfortunately for him, this area of Africa's rate of upthrust change is not rapid enough to enable the Richat to be below sea level as recently as he would hope. That doesn't mean everything he thinks is flat wrong. Just this part. As I covered in my longer paper, there's almost certainly an "Atlantean" colonization happening in the Sahara, but we won't know until we clear away the sand, which probably fell from either the Moon (and was transformed) or from Mars or Venus. Either way, it's an electrical hindrance to meteorology there nowadays, and a nuisance. We need pulverized sand, anyhow.⁵⁸ It'd be a good idea if for 1,000 years we terraform the Sahara and unveil this civilization, which likely will be either stone age *or* remnants of a fairly advanced engineering civilization that discovered piezoelectricity and acid-ion manufacture. The gold in Mauritania indicates whatever culture was there, would absolutely have been "obliterated" not by comet but by the thunderbolt connection, and potential mega-vortex (as per Andy Hall⁵⁹) at the location. Perhaps the Earth had a two way connection with tidal locking, with the Watcher/Moon or with Mars... or Metis, with one arc connecting the Sahara and the other to the vortex in Andy's California/Sacramento Valley hypothesis⁶⁰. Or perhaps multiple connections.

We do not know if the Devil's Tower is an anode and the Black Hills a cathode. We only know that the Devil's Tower formation story makes no sense, and the Crow and Chinese speak clearly about electrical origins for the Black Hills and Wudang Mountain. For that matter the aborigines of Australia also describe the same thing about Ayer's Rock as the Creek for Stone mountain: anode behavior and sudden uplift. It is clear there are multiple scales of these events, which makes judging the Richat (and anything that could reverse-terraform the Sahara, and crush the Azores) difficult. Suffice it to say, if the Big Sink was 5-15x the strength of Bikini Island hydrogen bomb⁶¹, then these events would exceed the energy required to destroy mountains and valleys⁶², even continents. And they would not spray Yucatan amounts of sun-choking nanodiamonds, but instead leave long transmuted precious metal veins, and instantly petrified coal deposits, as found with OOPArts and P. Mupp's crabs⁶³ and even a whole wooly

⁵⁴ https://www.academia.edu/44857386/Opinion_Big_Bang_Not_a_Cosmology

⁵⁵ HD 140283 <https://www.space.com/how-can-a-star-be-older-than-the-universe.html>

⁵⁶ <https://www.amazon.com/Seeing-Red-Redshifts-Cosmology-Academic/dp/0968368905>

⁵⁷ Effectively ending Big Bang's whole career.

⁵⁸ <https://www.cnn.com/2021/03/05/sand-shortage-the-world-is-running-out-of-a-crucial-commodity.html>

⁵⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a8C2OdSbw84>

⁶⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ecDDczFogR0>

⁶¹ See Appendix A, Figure 26

⁶² Compare to the Psalms

⁶³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5vOMGQTjW9k>

mammoth.⁶⁴ That kind of energy is how you wipe out megafauna, and leave everything else alive. Struggling, but alive. Even a single pulse Perattian thunderbolt might propagate 60,000 km of deadly current, using Uman's lightning propagation formula⁶⁵.

11. I tend to agree, 1 million years is something to "throw around." But for geologists it seems to them like a small amount of time.⁶⁶
12. As I mentioned, concentric motifs are found at least in Kentucky, Peru, and Africa. Concentric circle craters are found on the moon, Mars⁶⁷, Iapetus⁶⁸, etc.
13. Debunking any hope of this being Atlantis.
14. Here is where I tried to reach out to Jimmy before, and provide him the data to look at this. We are going to cross examine multiple imagery, and get a better understanding of how this site never could have held water.

Figure 4 - Richat Structure; note the supposed "south port" from his interview... the sand is flowing uphill, yet the entire crater is not level. The apparent circles are not concentric. There are no mountains to its north but it is up on a plateau, if anything. In fact, the site probably attracted a thunderbolt, whose Birkeland Currents rotate concentrically in shells due to what's called a "Bessel Function" which replaces the Lorentzian "right hand rule" with a 90 degree "phase shift" between electric and magnetic flux, because it was up high on a mineral bed. This is why the Kentucky Denisovan dome attracted the Big Sink Jovian era thunderbolt strike: it was on top of a limestone dome already. The Jephtha bolide strike may, or may not, have to do with the same dome. But the Fort Knox cryptoexplosive dome being on the edge of that larger dome and between it and western karst plains and within the Lichtenburg Knobs Region, is certainly not coincidental. One should expect to see similar karst behavior here, beneath the sands. Credit: Wiki

⁶⁴ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qzyDm_BegGA

⁶⁵ Maybe more if switching from spherical to cylindrical propagation.

⁶⁶ Reminds me of a saying, "1 billion here and 1 billion there, pretty soon you're talking about real money."

⁶⁷ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tRV1e5_tB6Y

⁶⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3ngA-WqVcno>

Figure 5 - 3d Lidar topography. Again note the asymmetric shape (typical of Birkeland filaments), the non-symmetric, non-uniform height of the so called concentric rings. Note that the canals do not meet (and a megatsunami would not cause those splayed fractures), and that they could not hold water. Note that the “south port” would have also drained all water away. The blue color has nothing to do with water, as he says, but with elevation. The collection of salt is from either the megatsunami or typical flash flooding and long term deposition - or both. The other edges to the north show some amount of electrical excavation, but it needs more examination up close. Andy Halls’ prediction likely would be to see sputtering discharge remains: bubbling, half arches, etc. The south “port” lead out is exactly reminiscent of the (definitely non volcanic) Upheaval Dome^{69 70} in the next figure. Credit: GeomapApp

⁶⁹ <http://www.iiisci.org/journal/pdv/sci/pdfs/ZA014LF20r.pdf>

⁷⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/hawthorne>

Figure 6 - Upheaval Dome; credit: Utah Geological Survey⁷¹

⁷¹ <https://geology.utah.gov/map-pub/survey-notes/geosights/upheaval-dome/>

Figure 7 - Isometric view from the North, from space; credit: C Hormann; please note the vertical dune ridges, which are probably formed by wind but would indicate the difficulty of water to *ascend* to the plateau. More importantly note that the obvious downhill nature of the feature is shown as more sand has accumulated here at the “southport” demonstrating that the feature - like this theory - could never “hold water.” Jimmy has staked his reputation on something that he himself has debunked where he presented it, and that’s unfortunate.

Figure 8 - Lidar; immediately note that the south port and east “coast” are at the same approximate level as the supposed rings. Just like Barringer Crater we can expect non-impact cryptoexplosive events (aso the Carolina Bays) to leave nearby geology relatively unaffected. But we can also see that to keep water inside the crater would be impossible. If the water also rose to the level to surround the rings, it would drown the center. There is no room for anyone to live. There are no concentric canals. This is a giant nothing burger as far as Atlantis is concerned. It is, however, a fantastic site for further electrogeological study. credit: M. Hurst/JAXA⁷²

⁷² <https://www.sciencephoto.com/media/1076871/view/richat-structure-lidar-satellite-image>

Figure 9 - Richat Topographical Map⁷³ ; again note the asymmetry and the fracturing and fault lines.

⁷³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OmNYIMmsrnk>

Figure 10 - This is a very large feature, and quite “striking” (no pun intended), however, it is not 300 x 230 miles wide. The elevation map here shows how far and away from possibility this is from Atlantis. At no point in any remote or recent past was this feature anywhere near the Atlantic Ocean. However, although there are not spectacular mountains nearby, as per the myth, we do see some interesting ridge formations, whose serpentine-like motion reflects Shiprock behaviors, and may warrant further investigation. The question would remain: if the knobs region of Kentucky had lighteningburgs of ~900 ft elevation, and rotated around the dome, where are the similar type features here? Could the arc have been a totally locked body, or are many? features buried beneath the sands? The energy required to make this formation would be orders of magnitude stronger than what is seen on Io’s or Enceledus’ electrovolcanism. However, does not appear to be the scale of what made the massive megavolcanoes

on Mars and Venus when they were in conjunction⁷⁴. That was, by all accounts, a direct arc connection. How long did this body arc with Earth, and was it the Moon? The moon's dust also does not grow plants, could the Saharan sands be partially transmuted moon dust? In the appendix of this paper I may examine this in chemical composition and comparison. The Moon is electro tidally locked, and has many electric crater evidence and arc discharge machining⁷⁵; credit: Wiki Commons

15. Joe is attempting to lead his expert witness here to make a definitive statement, and I'm afraid he's disappointed. Jimmy has not done the requisite analysis to see what would happen if water were inside of this, and he really could not. However, the author knows of one tool which may help, floodmap.net

Figure 11 - at 395m of flooding (1295 feet), the entire feature does form an “island” in the “ocean”, however (aside from the fact that the region was not underwater...)

⁷⁴ Both of which are way out of order of magnitude for the amount of tectonic activity known to be occurring, as compared to say Io or Earth which are far more active.

⁷⁵ See the Megafauna Extinction paper “P Plates” ^

FloodMap
 NEW! Color FloodMap
 NEW! Color ElevationMap

Elevation/Height/Water Level (-/+):

395
 meter.

Click on the Map to get/set the flood water level at the location.

Figure 12 - We can see that it is definitely not holding water or symmetric. The concentric rings disappear pretty fast on the outside and there isn't even a complete flooding around the core. Because the elevation is not level.

FloodMap
 NEW! Color FloodMap
 NEW! Color ElevationMap

Elevation/Height/Water Level (-/+):

400
 meter.

Click on the Map to get/set the flood water level at the location.

Figure 13 - the situation worsens as we go up by 5m increments. The settleable land rapidly recedes, and we still are not an island. Worse, our "port" doesn't connect to the "ocean"

FloodMap
 NEW! Color FloodMap
 NEW! Color ElevationMap

Elevation/Height/Water Level (-/+):

405
meter.

Click on the Map to get/set the flood water level at the location.

Figure 14 - We finally have our island city, it is rather small, and yet the port does not connect to the ocean.

FloodMap
 NEW! Color FloodMap
 NEW! Color ElevationMap

Elevation/Height/Water Level (-/+):

410
meter.

Click on the Map to get/set the flood water level at the location.

Figure 15 - No matter how high we raise the water, we cannot get it to touch the ocean. Yet creekbed evidence suggests the water would flow out, immediately.

16. Elevation I should think.
17. Again, this is a fallacy. Salt beds form in dry regions because they still get precipitation and then flow down to low areas. The minerals in the ground gather, and then the evaporation leaves them behind.
18. The leading of the witness here leads to erroneous conclusions.

19. Again, so Jimmy is completely aware of his mistake. He is ignoring it. I don't think it's for fame or grifting. I have no idea how much money his video has made him or anyone with Richat merch. I can certainly say that Atlantology is full of grifters, particularly those that want to go scuba diving in the Bahamas and sell books. There are also those that make fake Lidar and other information to mislead people. Regardless, by accident or purpose, this very unassuming and gentle man has misled millions of people on this subject and he should make a retraction, post haste.
20. These are trained experts, who even with their reliance on faulty ideas, are not wrong about this area. Of the regions that are curious for sudden upthrust and downthrust, there are known locations. I am going to reproduce a table that came from Allan and Declair⁷⁶, which I reproduced in a cited work:

Table 1 - Example evidence of Uplift and Submersion corollaries

Landmass	Uplift Region/value	Downthrust Region/Value
South American Andes	Perú, Bolivia, Titicaca (4 km) ⁷⁷	
North America	Cascades, Sierras	Guyana, Florida, Appalachia ⁷⁸ (3.2km)
Pacific Coast		Marianas, Philippines
Mid-Atlantic Ridge/Azores		Davis Strait (1.1 km+)
Pacific Ridge		Hawaii, Easter Island
African Rift Valley	Kenya, Tanzania	Anti-Atlas Mountains (2-3 miles)
Western Atlantic		Caribbean, Appalachia
North Atlantic		Greenland, Norway (2.75 km)
Eastern Atlantic		African coast, Canary Isles
Southwestern Pacific	Torres Strait, New Zealand (18 km) ⁷⁹	New South Wales, Indonesia
The Orient	Tibet (3km), Bayan Kara (2 km)	Japan, Indochina (50-300 ft), Sea of Okhotsk, Gobi Desert (600-900m)
Western Europe	British Isles, Alps (~3.7-4 km)	Gibraltar
Eastern Europe	Ural Mountains	Aegean Sea
Indian Subcont+Ocean	Kashmir (6k ft - 1.5 km)	Ganges (2 km of fill)

Please note that the Earth also is surrounded by a 64,000 km (40k miles) *crack* that wraps all around it.⁸⁰

Please Understand that if the Anti-Atlas Mountains are known to have massive changes, the catastrophist geologists would have noted it and recorded it for this area!

⁷⁶ <https://www.amazon.com/When-Earth-Nearly-Died-Catastrophic/dp/B00MF1AOTE>

⁷⁷ Values from "When the Earth Nearly Died", D.S. Allan & J.B. Delair

⁷⁸ aka North Atlantis, *ibid.* P. 33

⁷⁹ "With a horizontal displacement of similar magnitude.", *ibid.* P. 34

⁸⁰ *ibid.* p. 35-36

Figure 16 - Anti-Atlas Mountains; credit: Wiki

21. Correct. From rainwater deposition mostly. Probably also a single megatsunami event, which yes, left whale carcasses inland in Algeria, Tunisia, etc.
22. This is incorrect, as has already been shown.
23. Immediately around it is higher, but more pertinently the entire region is far too high to have been under the ocean
24. This comment makes me giggle because of the phraseology. Nevertheless, it's the JRE podcast. But salt is not a surprise in desert beds where water runs in and dries out, or flows out.
25. This saddens me. First, Randall is a friend/colleague⁸¹, and I don't think he's been done justice. Second, it'd be nice to know if Randall read the Atlantis paper I passed to him. He probably already had this personal theory, many have. But I'd like to know if he encouraged Jimmy to read it. I posted the link to Jimmy's video years ago, and have repeatedly exhorted him. He once asked me, "Then what else could it be?" and I answered him. The following are data I passed to him **3 years ago**, in direct reply to his OP on his part 2 video⁸²

"I will admit that this is a far better video than your first, and an excellent rebuttal to Matt's video. And you're right: they could have (and would have) chosen the site for it being a Thunderbolt Strike.

You're also right that a flowing megatsunami would rise like an ocean and swallow up "in a day and a night" we see this at the Japanese tsunami port videos. Considering the height of the mountains it would take about a day. Once drained, the evidence would be gone.

The main issue I am having, and why I think Matt's Frisland (which is certainly too late) and the Azores is a better option is the geology.

<https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/.../2005TC001836>

and

<http://eprints.esc.cam.ac.uk/3242/7/jgrf20376.pdf>

*We are seeing 1km at most (probably 0) over 5 Myr, or about 0.04 mm/yr
1km, (max) is about 3200 ft, which over 5 years is 0.0006" /yr.*

⁸¹ He passed me three of the papers he mentioned from the JRE podcast.

⁸² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lyV8TUIV3Ds>

This isn't like the uplift of Antarctica. Well, you say, "Ramon, by your own HEGEME theory, the earth's crust can deform rapidly, rise and shift, in spurts and have peaks and valleys, and in electric geology this can be accomplished in rapid clicks of time"

OK, let's open my table from "Unboxing Atlantis"

... ah I see here NO UPLIFT and in fact, probably downthrust.

Actually several places can and have had MASSIVE upthrust since YD. See Table 2 of my paper. But not this area.

Now, as to some of the more interesting points:

paleolithic finds: irrelevant, made by too many cultures

stone balls: made worldwide, not in Atlantean period by Archaic Period

Elephants: also found worldwide 12kya

Well in center: mere function of the higher aquifer

Concentric rings: actually there are too many of them and they don't match. The size, I admit is uncanny. I liked how you included the floodmaps, but those are simulations and notoriously goofy in practical value. They give rough ideas, but you have to go and take real soil samples.

Look, recently we at the AKHA conducted a survey for what we thought was almost assuredly a stone fort here in KY. But as you can see in this report, it was not. You have to go on site to conduct.

So I offer this. Let's go. I can afford it. Let's do Frisland, and let's do the Eye of the Sahara. Make a 10 year plan. I know people, and we can raise all the money we would need.

But I want to caution you... you can't use satellite imagery alone to prove anything.

But I admit, you and Matt have me intrigued I am going to make a part 2 paper for both of these locations and dig deep into the research, and try to find as good a LiDAR as can be found.

At this point I have to give you the slight edge only because Frisland was clearly around late enough for a map to exist of it.

But you have major problems here with the upthrust, as you know it is way too high in elevation to be IN the ocean or even near it. The megatsunami bit I can EASILY swallow. When you read "Unboxing Atlantis" I explain how very easily the HEGEME can shift and cause the membranous crust to deform and change elevations and move water about.

The issue here is... where's the massive change? Just where is it?

I'm not saying you're wrong, but you should @ me to discuss this or at least respond to the reports I have pasted.

PS your use of the floodmap creates pretty big issues for Giza "

I also included a reply link to the AKHA paper/report.

I do not see this comment anymore. I cannot think that the guy I Patron would delete this?

This is an overall positive comment, but as I have noted, it is not the end of discussion.

I agree to this OP above: it needs to be excavated.

So let's go. We'll create a thinktank."

An interesting find:

https://eoimages.gsfc.nasa.gov/images/imagerecords/4000/4602/PIA04963_lrg.jpg

src: <https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/images/4602/richat-structure-mauritania>

Houston, we have a problem and its name is levelness.

Faults that may or may not help your case (depends on excavations)

<https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/images/92071/richat-structure> “

Data selection matters <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oepey1q7TdM>

26. Neither I, nor Jimmy, nor probably Randall are exactly qualified bathymetrists to talk about high-speed laminar and semi-turbulent flow. However, there is some accuracy when speaking of long wavy dunes. However, Joe's skepticism is beginning to kick in, and rightfully so, as he realises Jimmy has not thoroughly analyzed the possibilities. Wind motion is far more likely to cause most of the dune features we see here. The rocks, if they are errata, would certainly be worth a **close examination**, but even common errata are often highly disputed between glacial and fluvial mechanisms. Bear in mind it took decades to sell the moving stones of Death Valley.
27. Non-sequitur
28. Again, self-similarity happens all the time in nature. The ridges of mountains are found in microscopy. It doesn't immediately follow that dunes which look like ocean beds are from it. There is also the potential of high force winds. Liquid and gas are both fluids and fluid dynamics are a hot topic in supercomputing for a reason. High variability.
29. I think Jimmy is [paraphrasing] from <https://news.mit.edu/2013/sahara-was-far-less-dusty-than-today-0405> which states 5kya. I originally saw 7kya. It's all in the Archaic period, so fits within EPEMC guidelines. Nevertheless his claim checks out. However, it also nukes his theory, for if the area was savanna 5kya, then there was no sand generally for to leave salt evidence. This is a massive logical fallacy. Probably unrecoverable.
30. This is true, but the green of the Sahara supports Atlantean period potential civilizations, and not a city in Mauritania. Again, he has undermined his own hypothesis.
31. It isn't an ocean because they were large freshwater lakes which still exist.

Figure 17 - Lakes of the Saharan Plains; credit: historyofyesterday.com⁸³

⁸³ <https://historyofyesterday.com/the-mysterious-people-that-lived-in-the-green-sahara-f993fe30a9d9>

32. Irrelevant? If anything, water flowing downhill towards an ocean negates the idea of an inland sea.
33. Again he feels this is a strong point, but instead it is a strong counterpoint, whether this is a fluvial discussion or an electrogeology discussion.
34. Regardless, it is too small to be a continent, and also too small to house millions of people without, as he admits, skyscrapers. If there had been skyscrapers, or even the stone towers of Tibet, then there would be structural remains.
35. See previous flood figures, Joe. It would be nowhere near 30 miles. Even using Tenochtitlan as a comparative template, it could never house millions of people.
36. This is where Jimmy's narrative begins to crescendo in a bad way. He feels he is making a strong case, but it is not adding up. First you rely on Solon, allegedly, but then say that the precision of the story is not a key detail. That is a colossal mistake. Secondly, the story as given is an order of magnitude size difference. For comparison let us look at the Azorean plateau:

Figure 18 - Azorean Plateau⁸⁴ Bathymetry; credit: C. Adam et al⁸⁵

At the middle of the plateau to the easternmost tip is ~410 mi long, and across a presumed average “height” the measure is ~262 mi. That makes one think that the potentiality is there, especially as the islands over this hotspot are still quite active.

37. Not necessarily. Cahokia was once larger than London and sported many advanced features, and it was estimated at 10,000-20,000 people.⁸⁶
38. This reminds me of the fallacies made by the Fyre Festival guys, underestimating the amount of land area needed for urban living, even in an importing and fishing based society. In reality, the Richat is incredibly small for millions of people. I do not believe an Atlantean city would need millions of people. Dozens of thousands would be extraordinary for the time. And rural people would view any disasters it faced as a result of angering the gods and/or living in Sodom like sin. Again the only sin for certain with Sodom as listed is that the citizens were rude and wanted to take the messengers to bed. Consider then what rural writers would think of a seafaring colonial power building (potentially) ziggurats and pyramids, and putting⁸⁷ stones with [alleged] handbag power sources (the Virocochan hypothesis).

⁸⁴ $4 \times 10^5 \text{ km}^2$

⁸⁵ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0012821X12006231>

⁸⁶ <https://www.livescience.com/22737-cahokia.html>

⁸⁷ I.e., crystal lattice liquefaction or decreasing viscosity

39. Joe is testing Jimmy's hypothesis out, and trying to figure out: should the water be in the ring's central looking canal, or between the rings and people who live upon the rings. Jimmy is himself not clear on this.
40. It certainly did, by high density electric current, counter-rotating. The asymmetry is absolutely key. Rapid excavation has been demonstrated by Yelverton, Gable, Hall, et al... That is to say **in lab evidence**
41. I'm disappointed Joe would say this. And heartened that his inner skeptical mind then wondered if he should.
42. I don't think he is quoting Randall at all, but paraphrasing a phone conversation. Randall is a jovial phone conversationalist, and like myself, he talks above people's understanding level. I don't think Jimm understands the turbulent flow concept.
43. Correct, Joe. Spot on.
44. True, that is the implication, but regardless this is *after* 5kya when sand appears. That leaves 7-8ky without any explanation. In fact it was more distance between then and the YDE start than from these dunes forming to now. That's an insurmountable problem for Jimmy's hypothesis because it exceeds any reasonable margin of error. And the YDE is all about the actions of years to hundreds of years, and chronology.
45. It seems to me that it is dawning on Joe that his skepticism is justified.
46. Hancock's theories and personal beliefs are a strong influence to Jimmy, and myself. I've been in communication with G. Hancock, but he was unwilling to take the time at this time to review all my data. That's fine, his choice. However, aside from proving Zamora cannot possibly be correct about the Michigan impact origin for Carolina Bays **before the Greenland Crater was announced**, I also stated in my Atlantis work that the Azores was a better candidate than any other. Jimmy's hypothesis came after. Now I'm not remotely the first to make this assertion, however, I am the first to make a quality paper on Atlantis summarizing the entire issue. When I look at the dating, therefore, please hear me out.

Assuming there was an Atlantis city proper, and not only a floating island archetype, and disregarding advancement and geometry, the fact would be that the civilization would only have been destroyed at the end of the YDE when the seas rose precipitously. The YDE, if it was a proto ice age, then it would have lowered ocean levels, leading to the Richat being far further away than now. See the following figure:

Figure 19 - Post Glacial Sea Level Rise; credit: Eupedia Forums⁸⁸

Regardless, the issue is that the Greenland “impact” which has similar features as per Upheaval Dome and Richat, and for which we have not excavated and do not know the fracturing yet, occurred 14.8kya, and Atlantis was 11.6kya. This tells me that the start of the Death of Shamash was 15kya, which is why Gunung Padang was abandoned, and then 12kya the Tepe Period began. When it crescendoed, there was some shift, potentially, and the Azores and other masses began sinking while ocean levels continuously rose. However, the “comet” impact had nothing whatsoever to do with Solon’s Atlantis. 3,000 years of separation is an enormous period of time in electrogeology.

47. This is where Jimmy’s narrative reaches the zenith of preparation and at the same time falls apart.
48. Joe is exactly right to deny this is scientific evidence Jimmy’s body language shifting from excited and scholarly to a dark shade of disappointment and then disseminating underscores his own uncertainty about his hypothesis.
49. I am disappointed with this moment, and for Jimmy. If he is so proud of his hypothesis, why is he so reluctant? If he is reluctant, why promote it so hard?
50. The YDB field:

Figure 20 - YDB Field, and sample locations. So Joe’s idea is based upon real, ongoing work, and checks out.

Tritinite: “Tritinite, also known as atomsite or Alamogordo glass,^{[1][2]} is the glassy residue left on the desert floor after the [plutonium-based Trinity nuclear bomb test](#) on July 16, 1945, near [Alamogordo, New Mexico](#). The glass is primarily composed of [arkosic](#) sand composed of [quartz](#) grains and [feldspar](#) (both [microcline](#) and smaller amount of [plagioclase](#) with small amount of [calcite](#), [hornblende](#) and [augite](#) in a [matrix](#) of sandy [clay](#))^{[3][full citation needed]} that was melted by the atomic blast. It was first academically described in [American Mineralogist](#) in 1948.^[4] It is usually a light green, although red trinitite was also found in one section of the blast site,^[4] and rare pieces of black trinitite also formed.^[5] It is mildly radioactive but safe to handle.^{[6][7][8]} Pieces of the material may still be found at the Trinity site as of 2018,^[9] although most of it was bulldozed and buried by the [United States Atomic Energy Commission](#) in 1953.^[10]”⁸⁹

⁸⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tritinitite>

51. This is a credible statement, and a good skeptical way to end this segment of the podcast. Joe is correct, we do not know how sophisticated, except that we know they were using symbols, recording sky events, carving relief, laying stone, carving the earth and burying previous stages of the star's breakdown, and living and working in the area. It was incredibly important at all the Tepe sites and nearby satellites to each central site, and culturally there was a significance to building these sites on cosmic hills, similar as per the Caer Melyn hill⁹⁰. These "potbelly hills" were representative of the star god's own pregnant mounding, as shown in the Vulture Stone, which is in the "hatching" portion of Enclosure D. The stone itself shows this mounding. That means these people were much more sophisticated, astronomically, than the stonehenge site, which came later. But compared to the imagery recorded at the Columbian Rock Art which reveal the actual anode tufting and birkeland currents forming, the art is much cruder.

Figure 21 - Vulture Stone; notice the attraction between the larger and smaller body. The larger appears to be Shamash/Ra (diameter ratio of 1.23), with potentially a Mars collinear alignment. The extended beak repeats as leg motifs worldwide (dromos in next figure).

The removed dimple "eye" of the "vulture" has not been identified. Most rocky bodies have a DR of 1.0.

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https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

Figure 22 - Gobekli Tepe layout (what 10% has been excavated); credit: S. Dendrinou⁹¹

Conclusion

In conclusion I'd like to see Jimmy either clarify his positions or evolve the hypothesis. Certainly I'd like him to stop misleading people on this hypothesis, as it literally does not "hold water." We live in an era of many profound changing claims, and people will be easily confused and misled. I think Jimmy is a very good person. He's just interested in knowing what happened. But when fame and hype meet unpreparedness, we get problems in altstream theory, and this hurts the community when the M. Shermers of the world descend upon it. This theory is full of holes, like swiss cheese. I think it's unrecoverable, but that remains to be seen when the place is excavated.

As for proving it is the remnant of electro-crypto-explosive activity, it seems to be heading in that direction. Whereas the fact is that there's little in the fault data to indicate impact, and almost no reason to suspect volcanism.

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

⁹¹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/317433676_Gobekli_Tepe_a_6_th_millennium_BC_monument/figures?lo=1&utm_source=google&utm_medium=organic

Appendix A - Megafauna Extinction Vajra Calculations & Data

Table 5 - Proposed vectors for the End of Eastern Cultures

pre-Archaic	> 12,800 YBP	Early cavemen and Travelers	Younger Dryas cataclysm (moon) ; Shamash
Tepe Period transition	12,800-8,000 YBP	Atlantean remnants	End of Saturnian Age
Archaic	9,000-5,000 YBP ¹⁸¹	PaleoIndians and Europeans ¹⁸²	End of Jovian Age Deluge?
Allegewi First Phase	5,500-3,600 YBP	Atlantean or Amazonia remnants	Exodus Cataclysm (Venus) & Plague
Allegewi Second Phase	3,600-1,700 YBP	Allegewi Loyalists	Mars & 300 CE comet
Hopewell	3,600-1,000 YBP	Traveler ¹⁸³ -Indian mixing	Waning of the gods
Woodland Era	5,500-500 YBP	American Indian arrivals	Disease and warfare?
Miss. Culture	2,600-500 YBP	Hopewell-traveler mixing	Disease ¹⁸⁴ and flood ¹⁸⁵
Cahokia Dominance	1,700-500 YBP	Welsh/Celtic mixing	Warfare with Lakota
Ft. Ancient	1,300-300 YBP	Hopewell remnant +American Indian	Warfare, disease, depopulation
Mandan Remnants	500-200 YBP	Cahokians and other Miss. survivors	Smallpox and warfare with Lakota
Historic Indians	400YBP-present	Displaced survivors of smallpox and warfare	Warfare, mixing with white pioneer populations

Figure 23 - Proposed Vectors for the End of Eastern North American Cultures; credit: author⁹²

Please note the correction to the table. This paper proposed the moon for a source of energy for YDE, this has been retracted by the author, and the death of Shamash⁹³ has replaced it as the source of all electrical and kinetic (bolide) energies. The scorching of the Earth matches the Egyptian Priest's descriptions, according to Solon/Plato.

⁹² "Megafauna Extinction" paper 1, Ibid. pp. 31

⁹³ Addendum 2

We are going to perform the calculations at $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{2}$, and $\frac{1}{3}$ the distance as well and compare them in Table 10.

Table 10 - Vajra Calculations using Coulomb's Law & Capacitance⁴²⁵

	Full distance	$\frac{1}{2}$ distance	$\frac{1}{3}$ distance	$\frac{1}{4}$ distance
d (m)	3.84E+08	1.92E+08	1.28E+08	9.61E+07
C (F)	3.40E-06	1.70E-06	1.13E-06	8.51E-07
e (F/m)	1.31E+00	3.27E-01	1.45E-01	8.18E-02
V = 20MV/m*d	7.69E+15	3.84E+15	2.56E+15	1.92E+15
E (j)	2.01E+26	2.51E+25	7.42E+24	3.14E+24
E (kC)	4.80E+22	6.00E+21	1.77E+21	7.51E+20
Lightning Bolts	4.02E+16	5.02E+15	1.48E+15	6.29E+14
# Vajra to boil Antarctica ⁴²⁶	1.33E+05	1.66E+04	4.90E+03	2.08E+03
<i>Adjusting down (10³)</i>	2.01E+23	2.51E+22	7.42E+21	3.14E+21
E (kC)	4.80E+19	6.00E+18	1.77E+18	7.51E+17
Lightning Bolts	4.02E+13	5.02E+12	1.48E+12	6.29E+11
# Vajra to boil Antarctica	1.33E+02	1.66E+01	4.90E+00	2.08E+00

Bear in mind these are using a supremely high breakdown voltage of 20 MV/m, which may be higher, or lower, under certain unknown conditions. Assuming the fact of current movement through space already established by NASA/JPL/ESA, it can be assumed that there are, in fact, arc conditions which would substantially lower the values by 10^3 which in the equation becomes a change of 6 sigfigs, or a million X factor. However, we cannot know this breakdown voltage at this time as in-situ measurements during an arc even have not happened. Perhaps a well-placed probe onto Ceres or Io would enable this. Considering the probe would carry Earth's charge with it, this might be unlikely. And would a probe survive the arc measurement? The author does not know.

Prior to the adjust down of 10^3 j, some of the numbers do seem ridiculous. All of the numbers at full distance are ridiculous, but we also know that for at least the last several thousand years, mankind has been safe from the moon at the current average distance. So the real issue is the strikes that allegedly came at shorter distances. See figure 113 for author's proposed 2-dimensional idea of distance variation. Such behaviors can somewhat be simulated using Universal Sandbox² which provides only gravitational effects⁴²⁷, and so would not be affected in simulation by the Biefeld-Brown effect (electrokinetics)⁴²⁸.

Since $V=IR$, we can establish therefore a relatively reliable calculations. First we can calculate the breakdown impedance that will be *inside* the BC/flux tube. Then, by providing the resistances of the soils, we can establish the types of voltage and power (in kW) that will be supplied to the soil.

Table 11 - Vajra Calculations using MHD and Satellite data

	Minimum	Maximum	Avg	Limited
V	1.00E+06	1.00E+08	5.00E+07	2.00E+05
I	2.50E+05	5.00E+08	5.00E+06	6.50E+05
R (space)	4.00E+00	2.00E-01	1.00E+01	3.08E-01
R (soil)	3.00E+07	3.00E+10	1.00E+08	1.00E+08
V (discharge)	7.50E+12	1.50E+19	5.00E+14	6.50E+13
P (V*I)/1000=kW	1.88E+15	7.50E+24	2.50E+18	4.23E+16

Comparing Table 10 and 11, we see that the voltages hover from 10^{-3} to 10^4 higher in Table 11. The avg expected voltage to soil is 10^{-1} than table 10. So the delivery power is *expected* to be about an order of magnitude smaller than in table 10, not 10^{-3} . Nevertheless, within reasonability, we are arriving at the "understanding" of what we are dealing with. That is to say from 1.88 exa-watts to 7.5 volta-watts, with an expected avg of 2.5 zetta-watts, and a assumed limitation of 42.3 exa-watts.

The average lightning stroke, as per Dwyer & Uman, lasts about 20-30 microseconds. We are assuming here that the Vajras are behaving similarly, although we have previously stated they won't, and certain sites demonstrate reliable geophysical evidence of prolonged return strokes and charge pumping (to saturation). However, to establish conservative boundaries (because the upper end cannot be known), we will use the 30 microsecond value to calculate, again, the joules and kC:

Table 12 - Energy values at the upper and lower limits

	Minimum	Maximum	Avg	Limited
joules in $.3 \times 10^{-6}$ s	5.63E+11	2.25E+21	7.50E+14	1.27E+13
E (kC)	1.34E+08	5.38E+17	1.79E+11	3.03E+09
Lightning Bolts	1.13E+02	4.50E+11	1.50E+05	2.54E+03
Upper Boundary (j)	5.63E+15	2.25E+25	7.50E+18	1.27E+17
Lower Boundary (j)	5.63E+08	2.25E+18	7.50E+11	1.27E+10
Avg Limit (j)	5.63E+10	2.25E+20	7.50E+13	1.27E+12

continuing unabated and Saturn is, electrically, dying as a planetoid/moon producing body (topping out at over 100 children!)

⁴⁵³ In lightning, step leaders are 100-300 A while strokes are 10-300 kA, a potential 1000x (10^3) increase

⁹⁴ Ibid. pp. 108

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	Minimum	Maximum	Avg	Limited
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E (kC)	1.34E+08	5.38E+17	1.79E+11	3.03E+09
Lightning Bolts	1.13E+02	4.50E+11	1.50E+05	2.54E+03
Upper Boundary (j)	5.63E+15	2.25E+25	7.50E+18	1.27E+17
Lower Boundary (j)	5.63E+08	2.25E+18	7.50E+11	1.27E+10
Avg Limit (j)	5.63E+10	2.25E+20	7.50E+13	1.27E+12

continuing unabated and Saturn is, electrically, dying as a planetoid/moon producing body (topping out at over 100 children!)

⁴⁵³ In lightning, step leaders are 100-300 A while strokes are 10-300 kA, a potential 1000x (10^3) increase

⁴⁵⁴ <http://www.ee.co.za/article/principles-testing-methods-earth-ground-resistance.html>

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Note - the energy released in Bikini H-bomb was 8 M-ton TNT or $8 \times 10^6 \times 4.184 \times 10^9$ j/ton = $3.3472E+16$ j

It's important not to get hung up on the sigfigs because actual values are incalculable without *in situ* measurement, which is both impossible and unlikely. It'd be deadly at any rate.

So we see that at the lower boundary, such as a small strike sjie, we can expect a vajra to be worth 113 or so lightning bolts, while at the upper end, possibly 450 billion bolts, with an average of about 150-250 thousand bolts of typical lightning. This seems far more reasonable than our classical model. Moreover, it demonstrates a new problem: either the event would have to be massively prolonged (as is expected), or some other mechanism would need to be proposed or at least appended to this mechanism for the melting of the ice sheets. The author proposes that the meltdown was caused by four factors:

1. Change in ocean current behavior as HEME and PEC behaviors adapted to SSC changes
2. Change in orbit and tilt, altering slightly the received plasma characteristics, which slightly changed Earth's own PEC behaviors.
3. Vajra/thunderbolt mechanisms, and sure, some impacts
4. Tectonic heating caused by SSC changes due to shifting positions relative to the sun⁴⁵⁵

Figure 26 - Energy Values at the upper and lower limits of Vajra; credit: author⁹⁶

⁹⁵ Ibid. pp. 116

⁹⁶ Ibid. pp. 116-117

100,000 meters from strike center for (5.5), using 300 ohm for ground current and 700 ohm for body current. In the case of (5.5), 100 m wide from strike center yielded 119 kV **for the smallest current found** in Table 11.

Table 13 - Radial Propagation voltages based on Table 11

	V_min	V_max	V_avg	V_limit
100m	1.19E+05	2.39E+08	2.39E+06	3.10E+05
1000m	1.19E+04	2.39E+07	2.39E+05	3.10E+04
10000m	1.19E+03	2.39E+06	2.39E+04	3.10E+03

The drop-off in voltage using (5.6) is linear, but in Table 14, we see that according to the 3.5m footprint of the mammoth's position, it will drop off geometrically, with an imposed limit of potential killing power (again using the smallest Vajra) at 2000-2500 m (over 6,000 feet)

A couple things to note: the current may be deadlier for a human or other small animal, or it may be better, being a smaller step potential. Also, the resistivity of different bodies are different. The author does not know the true resistivity of a Columbian Mammoth, he expects it would be higher than 300hm but perhaps not as high as for a human since elephant species are renowned for sensitive feet with many nerves. Finally, there is the issue of core versus surface spread of the charge of the body. Given that the literature varies in how many mA it takes to stop a heart, the author will assume 10 mA is the safe current (as high as 30 mA may be considered deadly in houses) and then quote the author,

"At a current of 0.04 to 0.06 amperes, asphyxia may occur from prolonged contraction of the chest muscles... From Dalziel (1953) the threshold energy level for fibrillation of the 700 ohm individual... is about 350 j... If we linearly extrapolate to a 70 kilogram human, certainly a questionable extrapolation, the lethal energy is 4410 j."⁴⁷⁵

The question arises, what is the lethal energy for a dire wolf, mammoth, mastodon, or ground sloth? The author certainly does not know.

Figure 27 - Radial Propagation voltages based on Figure 25; credit: author⁹⁷/Uman et al.

⁹⁷ Ibid. pp. 124

Table 14 - Step Potential Calculations for Columbian Mammoth 3.5m footprint

Distances (m)	Voltages	I_ground @ 300ohm (mA)	I_body @ 700 ohm (mA)
100	3,346.37	11,154.56	4,780.53
200	931.85	3,106.16	1,331.21
300	429.90	1,432.99	614.14
400	246.44	821.45	352.05
500	159.53	531.78	227.90
600	111.64	372.13	159.48
700	82.47	274.91	117.82
800	63.40	211.35	90.58
900	50.26	167.53	71.80
1000	40.81	136.05	58.31
2000	10.32	34.41	14.75
3000	4.61	15.35	6.58
4000	2.60	8.65	3.71
5000	1.66	5.54	2.38
10000	0.42	1.39	0.60
100000	0.00	0.01	0.01

Voltages, I_ground @ 300ohm and I_body @ 700 ohm

Figure 28 - Step Potential Calculations for Columbian Mammoth (3.5m footprint); credit: author⁹⁸

⁹⁸ Ibid. pp. 125

stroke (no dart leader, pump mechanism, standard 30 microsecond burst). Already we see in figure 121 that these strikes are deadly for a human or mammoth out to 2000 m or more than a mile away.

Table 15 - Max and Limited Vajra Voltages and Currents

Voltages	<i>Maximum Vajra</i>		Voltages	<i>Limited Vajra</i>	
	I_ground (mA)	I_body (mA)		I_ground (mA)	I_body (mA)
6,692,736.04	22,309,120.14	9,561,051.49	8,700.56	29,001.86	12,429.37
1,863,695.98	6,212,319.95	2,662,422.84	2,422.80	8,076.02	3,461.15
859,791.22	2,865,970.73	1,228,273.17	1,117.73	3,725.76	1,596.76
492,870.55	1,642,901.85	704,100.79	640.73	2,135.77	915.33
319,066.80	1,063,556.01	455,809.72	414.79	1,382.62	592.55
223,278.98	744,263.27	318,969.97	290.26	967.54	414.66
164,945.29	549,817.63	235,636.13	214.43	714.76	306.33
126,808.88	422,696.27	181,155.54	164.85	549.51	235.50
100,517.64	335,058.81	143,596.63	130.67	435.58	186.68
81,629.50	272,098.32	116,613.57	106.12	353.73	151.60
20,646.41	68,821.37	29,494.87	26.84	89.47	38.34
9,212.01	30,706.71	13,160.02	11.98	39.92	17.11
5,191.88	17,306.26	7,416.97	6.75	22.50	9.64
3,326.70	11,089.00	4,752.43	4.32	14.42	6.18
833.63	2,778.76	1,190.90	1.08	3.61	1.55
8.35	27.85	11.93	0.01	0.04	0.02

The max powered Vajra remains deadly at 100,000 m (62 miles), which surely a location such as Devil's Tower+Black Hills would have been quite able to propagate that far, or further, given the soil type⁴⁷⁷. This would definitely constitute a power worth worshipping (same for Ayer's Rock, in Australia). But even the limited Vajra has potency out to 3000 - 4000 m (1.86 - 2.48 miles)! That is truly the power of the gods. This supplies us both our vector for selective worldwide extinction (not to mention Younger Dryas mechanism), but explains not only "out of place" geology, but also "out of place" anthropology.

Figure 29 - Max and Limited Vajra Voltages and Currents; credit: author⁹⁹

⁹⁹ Ibid. pp. 126

Table 16 - Weapons of the Gods Names or god who wielded them ^{480 481482}

	Greece	Babylonian	India [Norse]	Brittain/Celtic	Americas	China [Japan]
<i>Thunder...</i>		Sharur	Vajra [Mjolnir]	Caladbolg	Thunderbird	Jiu-feng (bird)
<i>Spear/Trident</i>	Poseidon		Vel/Trishula Pashupatastra	Lugh/Invincible Gae Bulg		[Ame-no-nuhoko]
<i>Sword</i>	Harpē		Asi Nandaka [Hq̄fuð]	Claíomh-Solais Fragarach Dyrnwyn		Gan Jiang Mo Xie/Ye [Kusanagi]
<i>Archery</i>	Apollo		Pinaka, etc ⁴⁸³			
<i>Winds</i>	Titans		"Seven Winds"		Jem of Kukulcan	
<i>Tectonics</i>	Titans	Tiamat cracked ½ by Marduk	Sinking of Dwaraka		Lakota Creator-God	
<i>Floods</i>	Titans	Enlil	Missile>sinking of Dwaraka			
<i>Blasts</i>	Titans		Narayanastra Brahmastra	Balor's Eye	Xiuhcoatl	
<i>Hammer, etc..</i>	Hephaestus	Sharur	Gada Agneyastra ⁴⁸⁴		Foot of God (Delaware)	Ruyi Jingu Bang

Figure 30 - Weapons of the Gods; Names or god who wielded them; credit: author¹⁰⁰

¹⁰⁰ Ibid. pp. 128

Appendix B - Moondust vs. The Sahara

- Composition of Moondust:
“The bulk chemical composition of lunar dust varies across the lunar surface, but is about **50% SiO₂, 15% Al₂O₃, 10% CaO, 10% MgO, 5% TiO₂ and 5-15% iron** (Table 1), with lesser amounts of sodium, potassium, chromium, zirconium.” (sic)¹⁰¹
- Composition of Saharan Sand:
“In samples of Saharan dust from 2005, the average composition of the dust particles was: **64% silicates, 14% sulfates, 6% quartz, 5% high calcium particles, 1% iron rich (hematite), 1% soot, and 9% other carbon rich particles** (carbonaceous material).” (sic)¹⁰²
- Composition of Martian Sand:
“The Mars rovers have used gas chromatography, mass spectrometry, and laser spectrometry to determine the composition of martian soil. Mars regolith is **mostly silicon dioxide and ferric oxide, with a fair amount of aluminum oxide, calcium oxide, and sulfur oxide.**” (sic)¹⁰³

Table 2 - Comparative Analysis of Moondust, Mar’s Dust, and Saharan Sand

<i>Sahara</i>	<i>Moon</i>	<i>Mars</i>	<i>Toxic?</i>
Silicates (various)	SiO ₂	SiO ₂	Non toxic
	Al ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	Non-toxic / insoluble
SiO ₄			Non-toxic
Ca			Non-toxic
	CaO (quicklime)	CaO	Toxic/irritant to skin
Fe ₂ O ₃			Toxic
Hydrocarbons ^{104 105}			Non-toxic
	MgO		Safe/Irritant to breathe
	TiO ₂		Non-toxic
		SO ₂	Highly Toxic
	Fe		Can be toxic

¹⁰¹ <https://www.lpi.usra.edu/decadal/leag/DavidJLofus.pdf>

¹⁰² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saharan_dust

¹⁰³ <https://cen.acs.org/articles/96/i1/build-settlements-Mars-ll-need.html>

¹⁰⁴ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/anie.201914115>

¹⁰⁵ We are reminded of I. Velikovsky’s theory of Venutian hydrocarbons; dating near to the Exodus period, the 5kya desertification could match his 2600 BCE dating of the Venus disaster.

From the author's perspective, the above table overall leans strongly towards a Venutian origin, but we don't know its composition yet.¹⁰⁶ The Moon's surface is definitely not strongly promoting life, and this has been proved with soil growth tests. However Mars can promote plant life. It is possible that the Sahara's weather systems transformed the minerals in the 5,000-7,000 years since "desertification."

*"We found germination and plant growth for both moon and Mars soil simulants. Our results are in line with earlier research on Arabidopsis thaliana and Tagetes patula [19]–[21] on moon regolith simulant and moon rock simulant, though **our results appear to be less promising**. Kozyrovska et al. [20] had blossoming plants of T. patula, where we had only one plant of Sinapsis arvensis that formed a flower butt, but died before flowering.*

*On average species in Martian soil simulant performed significantly better than plants in Earth soil with respect to biomass increment. Although the Earth soil used, which was coarse and very nutrient poor, is not the best soil to grow crops on, we expected it to perform at least as well as the other two soils. However, in the warmer periods it was difficult to keep the water content in the pots high enough, despite spraying twice a day. **The Mars soil simulant resembles loess-like soils from Europe and holds water better than the other two soils.** Moon soil simulant dried out fastest. It therefore is essential that further research on the physical characteristics of the extra-terrestrial soils is conducted, as well as the way they could be irrigated. The larger water holding capacity of Martian soil simulant may explain its better performance and, partly, the underperformance of moon soil simulant. The high pH may also explain the lagging growth on the moon soil simulant and also on the Earth soil. Important for plant growth is not only the presence of nutrients, but also the balance between them. Both soils are rather imbalanced for nutrients; where the artificial moon soil lacks nitrates, the artificial soil lacks of phosphate. If nutrients are added in future experiments this imbalance has to be corrected as well, besides the addition of nutrients itself. The presence of a high C-elementary content in the Mars soil simulant is surprising. We also chemically analysed organic matter content in the simulant, but that resulted in obviously wrong results. The standard procedure includes backing the soil at 550°C. The problem is that part of the oxides, especially the iron oxides, evaporates as well, clearly yielding wrong results. Nevertheless a part of the origin of the Carbon content may be from organic matter. It may be a result of the way the soil is 'harvested' on Hawaii, leaving traces of organic carbon in the soil. Kral et al. [22] found traces of organic material in the JSC-1 simulant. It may also partly explain why the Mars soil was able to hold water best, as organic matter is more capable of holding water than bare sand. There is no organic matter on Mars [2]–[6], as far as we now, so this would make the Mars simulant we used less suitable for experiments to investigate the potential of Mars soil, unless the experiment has as goal to test the potential of the soil after adding organic matter. In our experiment this was the reason to test the legumes. They can be used as green fertilizer and after growth mixed with the soil. Visual inspection of the Mars soil simulant did not reveal large quantities of organic matter. However, further test on the simulant is advisable.*

This experiment was carried out in pots. Some of the crops on Mars or moon may be cultivated in pots, but part of the crops may possibly be cultivated in full soil (in growth chambers or under domes). Moist conditions will then be different and may give rise to different results between pots and full soil. It is therefore of interest to conduct future experiments in full soil cultivation as well."¹⁰⁷

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.britannica.com/place/Venus-planet/Surface-composition>

¹⁰⁷ <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0103138>

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